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D3.3 - Workbenches and tools (notebooks, model, containers with instructions)

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Tasks	T3.2 Physics Workbench, T3.3 EOVS workbench for eutrophication: chlorophyll, nutrients, oxygen, T3.4 EOVS Workbench for ecosystems
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Executive Summary

This deliverable encompasses the workflows, tools and user documentation for the three analytical Workbenches developed within Work Package 3 of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project.

These Workbenches implement cloud-based analysis pipelines that enable ocean scientists, data managers and modellers - among others - to produce harmonised, high-quality Essential Ocean Variable (EOV) and Essential Biodiversity Variable (EBV) datasets more easily and rapidly, overcoming the fragmentation of marine data across heterogeneous infrastructures. They leverage on the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment and cloud-computing platform powered by D4Science, and can be customised to the user's needs.

The Physics Workbench (<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/physics-workbench>) enables users to integrate temperature and salinity data from four infrastructures – SeaDataNet, Copernicus Marine Service (CORA product), EuroARGO and World Ocean Database – through a workflow combining semantic harmonisation, quality control and duplicate detection, delivering added-value EOVS dataset that can be used in ocean reanalysis, climate normals, ocean monitoring indicators, and AI-driven applications. The Eutrophication Workbench (<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/eutrophication-workbench>) provides a cloud-based environment to generate harmonised, complete, deduplicated EOVS collection for chlorophyll-a, nutrients, and dissolved oxygen, federating data from Copernicus Marine Service, EMODNet Chemistry and the World Ocean Database, in line with GOOS recommendations. Both share a common technical foundation based on the BEACON datalake and semantic harmonisation, as well as common tools (CW Duplicates Detection tool for duplicate handling, WebODV for data exploration and visualization, FileForge for data conversion and annotation), with the exception of the MinMax Alert Tools used for additional quality control by the Physics Workbench only.

The Ecosystem Workbench (<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/ecosystem-workbench>) aims to improve the availability, quality and interoperability of marine plankton observations to diagnose EOVS and EBVs related to plankton biomass and diversity. It leverages the CEPHALOPOD species habitat modelling pipeline that combines automated data processing, machine learning and quality control to produce global spatial distribution estimates from heterogeneous observation types from major biological data initiatives such as GBIF, OBIS, AtlantECO, EcoTaxa, ELIXIR (MGnify). Outputs are accessible interactively through the Cephaloview application.

All three Workbenches, their notebooks and components are fully documented and designed to ensure the reproducibility of their results. They are open to external users, available for reuse under open-source licenses through the Blue-Cloud VRE and catalogue (<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/catalogue-bluecloud-cloud>) and open repositories (Git, Zenodo and Software Heritage). Their results are planned for

integration into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the European Digital Twin Ocean (EDITO) through the EOSC Node European Digital Twin Ocean.

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Physics Workbench Lab Users Handbook

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Task	T3.2 Physics Workbench
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1.0	30/06/2026	Simona Simoncelli (INGV)	Final version for submission

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
PWB	Physics Workbench
BC2026	Blue-Cloud2026
CORA	Coriolis Ocean Dataset for Reanalysis
NVS	NERC Vocabulary Server
SDN	SeaDataNet
WOD	World Ocean Database
BDI	Blue Data Infrastructure

Keywords

EOSC; Workbench; Blue Data Infrastructure, Data Lake, Quality Control, Duplicates, Notebooks, Workflow

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Abstract

The Blue Cloud2026 **Physics Workbench (PWB) Lab enables users to integrate Temperature and Salinity data from four Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs): SeaDataNet, Copernicus Marine Service (CORA product), EuroArgo and World Ocean Database.** The data integration includes the semantic harmonisation of a set of essential metadata variables. The integrated data-lake allows data and metadata sub-set or filtering. The extracted data pass through an additional quality control process to guarantee data quality consistency and potential duplicates are detected and handled. The result is an added value EOVs dataset ready to be used for assimilation in ocean reanalysis, for deriving multi-year data products, such as climate normals and ocean monitoring indicators. The dataset can also be used for AI data driven applications.

The Physics Workbench workflow is made by different components: the Beacon Data Lake with semantic harmonisation, the MinMax Alerts tool (quality control), the cw Duplicate tool (duplicates detection and handling), the FileForge tool (metadata annotation and format conversion) and the webODV tool (data visualization and analysis).

This handbook is made to guide the user through the execution of the PWB workflow that generated the final integrated EOVs dataset for the Mediterranean Sea on the Blue Cloud 2026 Virtual Research Environment (VRE).

Each component of the workflow could also be customized to serve the user needs, i.e. to obtain an integrated dataset in a different ocean region, in a different time period, applying different duplicate search criteria or using a different reference field in the quality control procedure.

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1. Introduction

Welcome to the Users Handbook for the Blue-Cloud2026 **Physics Workbench (PWB) Lab**. This handbook serves as a comprehensive guide, providing essential information and practical instructions for effectively utilizing this service. This handbook will evolve over time based on user feedback and advancements in the (PWB) Lab capabilities.

The Blue Cloud 2026 Physics Workbench Lab enables users to integrate physics essential Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) data from four Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs): [SeaDataNet](#), [Copernicus Marine Service \(CORA product\)](#), [EuroArgo](#) and [World Ocean Database](#). The objective was to implement a cloud-based workflow capable of subsetting and retrieving ocean Temperature and Salinity data from an harmonised and integrated data lake, to apply a quality control procedure and a duplicate detection tool in order to generate a ready to use and machine accessible dataset. The data goes through a statistical Quality Control (QC) to ensure quality consistency and a duplicate scan to identify duplicates and potential discards. A key tool then converts and annotates files (QC alerts, duplicates) enabling the full pre-operational workflow to generate an added value and easy to use BC2026 PWB EOVs dataset.

Data integration has been conceived for maximizing the availability of good quality data in a specific ocean region, allowing the derivation of added value products and applications reducing uncertainties.

The PWB workflow has been developed to preserve the full provenance and lineage information along the data value chain to acknowledge the multiple actors involved, i.e. technicians operating at sea, data managers, intermediary producers, IT developers.

This service can be classified as a system prototype demonstration in an operational environment (TRL 7), it has been developed on the D4Science platform exploiting its multiple generic services, specifically the Jupyter Lab and the [Cloud Computing Platform \(CCP\)](#) (Assante et al., 2019). All the workflow components have been developed, tested and deployed but its orchestration requires some manual intervention. The automation of the pipeline will be the main scope during the next phase in the framework of the [EOSC Node European Digital Twin Ocean](#).

The PWB prototype has been implemented as proof of concept to generate an integrated EOVs dataset for the Mediterranean Sea covering the time period from 1950 to 2025. However the workflow can be customized to a different ocean region and time span, but presently the PWB workflow implementation has limitations to tackle the global ocean or too wide ocean regions. Scaling up to the global ocean will be one of the main objectives in the next phase and will require both adequate computational resources and further optimization of the workflow implementation.

The PWB Lab workflow, schematized in Figure 1, is made by different components:

- the **Data Lake** made by the monolithic instances of the four BDIs and the merged instance;
- the **MinMax Alerts tool** (quality control);
- the **cw Duplicate tool** (duplicates detection and handling);
- the **FileForge tool** (metadata annotation and format conversion) and,
- the **webODV tool** (data visualization and analysis).

Figure 1 - Diagram of the Physics Workbench Lab

The PWB EOVs dataset is created at the end of the execution in two different versions, one augmented with duplicates annotation and the other cleaned from duplicates. The two dataset versions are provided in parquet and odv spreadsheet formats, to serve a wide user community and multiple downstream applications.

This handbook briefly describes the workflow components, then it presents the instructions for its execution.

All PWB resources are accessible at the [Blue Cloud 2026 Catalog](#) and are listed in the [Appendix](#). They are available for re-use in the Physics Workbench shared workspace for members of the [PWB Lab](#) which is accessible through the [Blue Cloud 2026 Gateway](#).

2. The Physics Workbench Data Lake

The PWB Data Lake relies on Beacon technology (<https://beacon-datalake.org/>), which is an open-source data lake query engine designed to make large collections of scientific data files directly, easily, and quickly queryable. It focuses primarily on environmental and observational datasets such as oceanographic and climate data but is extendible and proven to work well for other domains as well, as long as the input data follows any standard-like way of describing its contents. Users can request subsets by filtering variables,

time ranges, spatial regions, or metadata attributes, and Beacon automatically retrieves and harmonizes the relevant data across all matching files.

In January 2025, Beacon 1.0.0 was made publicly available as an open-source software, allowing everyone to set-up their own Beacon node to enhance the access to their data or use existing Beacon nodes from well-known data infrastructures such as Euro-Argo or the World Ocean Database (WOD) for fast and easy access to harmonized data subsets. More technical details, example applications, GitHub code, and general information on Beacon can be found on the website (<https://beacon-datalake.org/>).

Within the context of Blue-Cloud2026, Beacon has been deployed to provide access to harmonised subsets from Blue Data Infrastructures for researcher groups that aim to generate harmonised and validated data collections of EOVs. To this end a set of Infrastructure-specific Beacon nodes (monolithic instances) were set-up for relevant data collections that are easily accessible via notebooks in the Virtual Research Environment.

The PWB Lab enables users to efficiently access in situ temperature and salinity data from 4 BDIs: Copernicus Marine Service, SeaDataNet, Euro-Argo and the World Ocean Database.

CORA

The Global Ocean- CORA- In-situ Observations Yearly Delivery in Delayed Mode (CORA, *Szekely et al. 2025*) is ingested in two monoliths CORA-PR for profiles and CORA-TS for time series. Only CORA-PR instance is used in the PWB workflow. The CORA product is a global dataset of in situ temperature and salinity measurements. It assembles observations from many different sources collected by Coriolis data centre in collaboration with the In Situ Thematic Centre (INSTAC) of the Copernicus Marine Service (INSTAC).

The CORA monoliths are updated twice a year according to the product release time schedule.

SeaDataNet

[SeaDataNet](https://cdi.seadatanet.org/search) is a distributed BDI for the management of large and diverse sets of ocean data deriving from in situ measurements. The on-line data and metadata access is provided through a unique portal interconnecting the interoperable node platforms constituted by the SDN data centers, the Common Data Index (CDI) service (<https://cdi.seadatanet.org/search>).

The SeaDataNet monolith is updated weekly.

Argo

The international [Argo programme](#) was initiated in 1999 providing a global array of autonomous instruments, deployed over the world ocean, reporting subsurface ocean properties to a wide range of users via satellite transmission links to data centres. The [Euro-Argo](#) project involved in 2008 twelve European countries with a common aim to provide an optimized and sustained European contribution to Argo. The Euro-Argo European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) was established in 2014 and it is one of the Blue Cloud federated data infrastructures.

The Argo monolith is updated weekly.

World Ocean Database

The [World Ocean Database](#) (WOD) is the world's largest collection of uniformly formatted, quality controlled, publicly available ocean profile data. It is a powerful tool for oceanographic, climatic, and environmental research, and the end result of more than 20 years of coordinated efforts to incorporate data from institutions, agencies, individual researchers, and data recovery initiatives into a single database. The WOD consists of periodic major releases and quarterly updates to those releases.

The WOD monolith is updated quarterly.

The BDIs datasets with their full metadata description have been ingested in **monolithic data instances** (Figure 1) deployed in the D4Science platform. Please refer to the [Appendix](#) to get the links to the Blue Cloud catalog landing pages of the PWB monolithic instances.

The temperature and salinity data from the four **monolithic data instances** are then ingested and integrated in a **merged instance** (Figure 1) **with online semantic harmonization of a set of essential metadata variables**.

The challenge was to deliver an harmonised EOVs dataset, federated from the monolithic instances with different data models. To this scope the PWB team formulated a core metadata – data profile which has been populated by extracting and mapping metadata from the monolithic instances. [Deliverable D5.5](#) describes (see D5.5 Table 3) the adopted common metadata and data profile for the merged Beacon instance, including the target vocabularies. Table 1 below presents some new metadata fields that have been introduced to guarantee full traceability of the data lake content to its source BDI, where the full data and metadata reside.

	CORA	Argo	SeaDataNet	WOD
SOURCE_BDI	BEACON_CORA_PR	BEACON_ARGO	BEACON_SEADATANET	BEACON_WOD
BDI_SNAPSHOT_DATE	product release or BDI snapshot date			
BDI_MONOLITH_VERSION	Beacon monoliths version			
BDI_HARMONIZATION_DATE	date of harmonization (merged instance)			
SOURCE_BDI_DATASET_ID	DC_REFERENCE	PLATFORM_NUMBER +CYCLE_NUMBER +DIRECTION	LOCAL_CDI_ID+EDMO_CODE	WMO_UNIQUE_CAST

Table 1 – New metadata fields that have been introduced in the merged instance to guarantee the full data traceability to its source BDI, where the full data and metadata reside.

3. Semantic Harmonization

The harmonisation and standardisation effort within BC2026 aims at enabling faster integration, more accurate duplicate checks, and greater interoperability while minimising information loss and maintaining traceability.

It was applied to the diverse unit, coordinate reference system, time format and quality flag conventions used across the source BDIs, as well as the different labelling conventions used for variable names, observation platforms, measuring instruments.

The general approach to standardisation and semantic harmonisation within the BC2026 project is described in a number of Deliverables (e.g. [D3.1](#) and [D5.5](#)). In this section, we will focus on information related to the practical implementation of semantic harmonisation for the PWB.

The strategy and rules followed for the semantic harmonisation are as follows:

Parameters

The BODC P01 Parameter Usage Vocabulary (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/>) was the only parameter naming vocabulary capable of accommodating the range of variable naming practices in use in the different source BDIs. Using either SKOS mappings stored in the NVS or mappings hardcoded in Beacon, source parameter labels were matched to their exact or closest broader P01 parameter concept based on knowledge of what these labels represented and not just based on lexical matching.

- **Argo:** Uses its own R03 Argo parameter vocabulary (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R03/>) for its parameter naming. Mapping with P01 can be obtained from the NVS since many R03 concepts are mapped to a unique P01 equivalent concept with an owl:sameAs relationship.

- **CORA:** Uses CF Standard Names (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P07/>) and the P09 MEDATLAS Parameter Usage Vocabulary (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/>) for parameter labelling. P09 concepts are systematically mapped to P01 concepts by the P09 governance team at Ifremer hence these mappings were already available from the NVS. In the case of the CF Standard Names there is no consistent one-to-one mappings with P01. These were created manually for the BC2026 PWB use case and stored in Beacon.
- **SeaDataNet:** Uses P01 as its common variable naming convention hence data streams are already associated with a P01 code attributed by the data centre that provided the data to SeaDataNet. In addition, parameter groups are listed as coarser concepts at the Common Data Index (CDI) discovery level, using the P02 Parameter Discovery Vocabulary. Every P01 concept is mapped to one and only one broader P02 concept but one P02 concept can be mapped to many child P01 concepts covering a broad range of semantic granularity (from fine definitions that includes e.g. element of methodology, to broad concepts that contain the minimum amount of information required to define the variable unambiguously). Many of the latter are the ones used for data aggregation.
- **WOD:** uses its own internal codelists published in the WOD Manual (Garcia et al., 2024; Mishonov et al., 2023) and [web page](#). These were mapped manually to the closest broader P01 codes and stored in Beacon.

Units

Source units and their labels used for temperature and salinity data channels were standardised using the NVS P06 vocabulary (<https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/>).

Source units are read by Beacon and mapped to their matching concept from the NVS P06 vocabulary uniquely identified in Beacon by its URN (e.g. [SDN:P06::UPAA](#)) and its preferred label, e.g. “Degrees Celsius” for temperature, “metres” for depth, while salinity is “[dimensionless](#)”. The harmonisation of units by Beacon includes transformation of values based upon predefined rules.

Platforms

The common vocabulary used for platform harmonisation was the NVS L06 SeaVoX Platform Categories vocabulary (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/>). However, duplicate record identification across all BDIs but Argo, also benefits from having not only the platform type but also the platform instance identified accurately. This was done by mapping all non-Argo platform instances to the ICES platform code vocabulary using their NVS C17 unique URN (e.g. [SDN:C17::74E3](#)). Different methods had to be followed to map the source information from the various BDIs to their correct C17 code. Below is a summary of the different approaches.

- **Argo:** a single L06 (SDN:L06::46 for “drifting subsurface profiling float”) was attributed to data from Argo - this was sufficient at this stage but future improvements may look at also capturing the platform model using e.g. the B76 NVS vocabulary (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/B76/>). Argo platform instances are uniquely identified in the source file by their unique platform numbers.
- **CORA:** values in “ship_platform_number” are matched to the call sign in C17. Beacon uses the time at which the observation was made to ensure that the call sign is matched to the correct platform instance in the C17 vocabulary since the association between call signs and platform instances are not unique. L06 platform type URNs are derived from the CORA Data Type Bigram with a conditional criteria based on the value of the WMO_instrument_type.
- **SeaDataNet:** the C17 platform instance and/or L06 platform type are extracted from the CDI metadata record and directly inserted in their appropriate fields in Beacon.
- **WOD:** WOD maintains its own list of codes and names for platform instances¹. The WOD list was extracted and manually mapped to C17 concepts using a series of iterative matching methods that used a succession and combination of criteria including platform names, classes, countries, call signs, IMO numbers. A total of 470 platform (mainly ship) instances were mapped to their unique ICES platform identifiers from C17 with 100% certainty (close to 50% of the platform instances held in WOD). These mappings were used by Beacon to match incoming WMO platform IDs to a C17 URN and, using the mapping held in the NVS between C17 and L06, to the L06 category. These mappings have also been added to the Knowledge Base of the BODC Semantic Analyser so that they can be re-used by others.

Instruments

In Beacon, “instrument” is variable-specific and it represents a key element of the method used to create a measurement. The common vocabulary selected for the harmonisation of instruments (sensors or sampling devices) is the NVS L05 SeaDataNet device categories (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/>) which captures instrument types. Whenever possible, instrument models were also matched to their unique identifier from the NVS L22 SeaVoX Device Catalogue (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L22/>) however this information was not often available or, when available, it was not always easy to link it to a given variable. A review of how data models capture those elements of methodology will be needed in the future to ensure that a parameter can be easily connected to key elements of the methodology used to derive it.

¹ https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/world-ocean-database/CODES/s_3_platform.html

- **Argo**: the instrument field for temperature and salinity was populated from a mapping between Argo WMO_INST_TYPE and L05 or L22, hardcoded into Beacon. When no L05 or L22 could be found, the default generic L05 code for CTD was used.
- **CORA**: the instrument field for temperature and salinity was populated from a mapping between CORA WMO_INST_TYPE and L05 or L22, hardcoded in Beacon. Failing this, Beacon uses mapping established between the Data Type Bigram and L05 to fill the gaps. It was not always possible to populate this field and, in the future, effort will be needed to better harmonise this information across the BDIs.
- **SeaDataNet**: the variable-specific L22 codes were obtained from the metadata header of the SeaDataNet file. However if multiple L05 were present at the CDI-record level, the software currently selects the first encountered and this is not guaranteed to be the most appropriate one. Improvements to this metadata workflow will be addressed in the next phase.
- **WOD**: instrument type and model information was extracted from WOD code table v_5_instrument² which also contains information about platforms, and mapped to an exact L22 concept or the closest broader L22 or L05 concepts. These mappings are currently hardcoded in Beacon but will be made available via the BODC Semantic Analyser.

4. MinMax Alerts Tool

The **MinMax Alert Tool** (links to the BC2026 catalog landing pages in the [Appendix](#)) is a component of the PWB cloud-based workflow created by the POKaPOK team (<https://pokapok.org>) and deployed as a method on the D4Science [Cloud Computing Platform](#). The tool is in open source published on Zenodo (Weber et al., 2026).

The tool is based on the MinMax method (Gourrion et al. 2020). The MinMax method is a *local range* Quality Control procedure comparing each observed parameter value to local validity intervals. If a value falls outside such an interval, it is flagged as anomalous. These validity intervals are stored in reference fields provided by oceanography experts in netCDF format (Gourrion et al., 2026).

In the framework of the physical workbench, the MinMax Alert Tool applies the MinMax method to temperature and salinity in order to detect out of range measurements considered as probably bad. The tool operates on parquet observation files and produces annotated output files in the same format, which are then used to create the final EOVs (Essential Ocean Variables) dataset product.

² https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/world-ocean-database/CODES/v_5_instrument.html

The [MinMax Alerts tool user guide](#) provides detailed instructions on the software and its execution.

5. Duplicates Tool

The **cw Duplicate Tool** (links to the BC2026 catalog landing pages in the [Appendix](#)) is a component of the PWB cloud-based workflow created by the POKaPOK team (<https://pokapok.org>) and deployed as a method on the D4Science [Cloud Computing Platform](#). The tool is in open source published on Zenodo (Racapé et al., 2026).

The duplicates detection is based on basic but mandatory metadata that has been harmonized in Data Lake. The method generates a list of potential duplicates and computes some statistics. Then a decision tree is used to list the duplicates to be discarded. Two output files in csv format are produced and used to create the final EOVs dataset product: the list of duplicates is used by FileForge tool to generate the annotated version of parquet and odv spreadsheet files, and the list of discards to generate the cleaned version of parquet and odv spreadsheet files.

The [cw Duplicates tool user guide](#) provides detailed instructions on the software and its execution

6. FileForge Tool

The **FileForge tool** was created by the Ifremer team (<https://www.ifremer.fr/en>) and deployed on the D4Science as CCP method. FileForge (Couppey et al., 2026) is open source and available on [Ifremer's GitLab](#) (link to the BC2026 catalog landing page in the [Appendix](#)).

It converts parquet datasets into multiple output formats, including parquet and ODV spreadsheet files. During the conversion process, predefined data-processing operations can be applied to prepare and enrich or filter the dataset. Because each output format relies on distinct data models and metadata management systems, the tool adapts the data structure and metadata representation to exploit the specific capabilities of each format while preserving interoperability and data integrity.

In parquet, the metadata that is stored is primarily intended for internal file management, and the format does not provide a standardized mechanism for storing domain-specific metadata. An external metadata file, JSON-LD compliant with the CroissantML specification, has been introduced to address this limitation.

To accommodate the outputs produced by the upstream tools (Figure 1), several processing steps have been defined:

- Use the cw Duplicate tool csv output to identify duplicate profiles, maintain traceability to the original records, and annotate the affected profiles accordingly.
- Use the MinMax Alerts tool log file to determine the reference files employed during data flagging and annotate them in the EOVs dataset in both parquet and ODV spreadsheet formats.
- Use the cw Duplicate logs and MinMax logs to collect and record the software versions involved in the processing workflow and annotate them in the EOVs dataset in both parquet and odv spreadsheet formats.

The [FileForge Tool user guide](#) provides detailed instructions on the software and its execution.

7. PWB workflows

“Easy” Workflow

The PWB Lab enables the users to efficiently access in situ temperature and salinity data from the four BDI **monolithic instances** (links to the BC2026 catalog landing pages in the [Appendix](#)). The **Monoliths** (Figure 1 and Figure 2) with full metadata description are accessible for subsetting (in space and time) and filtering by metadata (i.e. by quality flag, data originator, instrument, platform) to obtain output files in multiple formats to be reused in customized workflows. The ODV spreadsheet format allows their import in webODV service for data exploration and further analysis.

Figure 2 - Diagram of the Physics Workbench Lab “Easy” workflow.

Jupyter Notebooks, one per BDI, to execute data queries are provided (links to the BC2026 catalog landing pages in the [Appendix](#)). They are self-explanatory and guide the user through proper subsetting and filtering. The notebooks are available for re-use in the Physics-Workbench shared workspace in the folder [Monoliths](#). **Example output datasets** (links to the BC2026 catalog landing pages in the [Appendix](#)) obtained from the query notebooks are also provided per each BDI.

Pre-operational Workflow

The pre-operational (pre-op) workflow diagram is provided in Figure 1 and its execution starts from querying the data lake merged instance. The [data query](#) has been built to extract in situ temperature and salinity profiles per each BDI in the Mediterranean Basin between 1950 to 2025.

The [query notebook](#) filters out in BEACON_CORA_PR, BEACON_SEADATANET and BEACON_WOD all *Profiling Floats* data which are gathered directly from BEACON_ARGO. Thanks to the weekly BEACON_ARGO update process this provides the latest and best version of Argo profiles without creating duplicates. The notebook saves variables in parquet output files and metadata variables in a JSON metadata file, which is further annotated by FileForge with lineage information from the CCP methods. It also integrates the POSITION_QC flag in BEACON_SEADATANET and BEACON_WOD parquet files using a simple check on coordinated falling at sea (1) or on land (4).

The MinMax Alerts tool uses the following reference fields with no widening option (Gourrion et al., 2026):

- Temperature : REF_MinMax_1D_TEMP_4H6_1_WF000_BS000_v20250320.nc;
- Salinity : REF_MinMax_1D_Psal_4H6_1_WF000_BS000_v20250320.nc.

The duplicate scan done by cw Duplicates tool is set to detect “exact duplicates”, profiles having the same coordinates (within 0.1 min distance in longitude and latitude), sampling time (1 minute) and instrument information. This first PWB implementation tackles the main type of duplicate but be aware that remaining duplicates may still exist in the EOVs dataset, as it will be discussed later on. This is a reason to provide also the *PWB EOVs dataset annotated version* which contains all the duplicate groups to be inspected by the users. It is suggested to explore the odv collections, either annotated or cleaned, available in the public webODV dataspace before any usage of the PWB EOVs dataset to verify if it fits to your purpose. webODV allows to run on the cleaned version its duplicate scan tool, which might also provide additional information to the user on the adequacy of the product.

The pre-op workflow can be executed:

- in **share-mode by the developers** using the D4Science shared dataspace and Physics-Workbench workspace;

- in **private-mode by the users** in the user’s workspace.

In **share-mode** the PWB team tested and implemented the workflow sharing notebooks, tools configurations and results for validation. Attention in the tools implementation has been put on the input/output procedures and executions to avoid conflicts and overwriting of the outputs.

In **private-mode** the user can replicate the workflow by cloning the data lake query notebook and using the shared input configuration files in the Physics-Workbench workspace. In order to replicate the PWB EOVs dataset the data lake query is not needed, since its re-run would generate different parquet files due to the data lake update process, and consequently different final results.

The final PWB EOVs dataset is obtained using the cw Duplicates tool version 1.2, the MinMax Alerts tool version 1.42 and FileForge version 0.1.28.

8. Physics Workbench Lab execution

Registration

To be able to access Blue-Cloud 2026 services, users first need to register to the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform by creating an account on the [Blue-Cloud 2026 Gateway](#) (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Blue-Cloud Gateway

The registration process ends with a pop-up advertising on “email verification” sent by the Blue Cloud management team. After the confirmation of registration, the user can start using the Blue Cloud platform. A video tutorial on how to register on Blue-Cloud is also available here: [Blue-Cloud Hackathon - Using the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment](#). The PWB Lab execution requires the access at

<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/physics-workbench/> (Figure 4) that allows to reach the PWB welcome page <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/physics-workbench> (Figure 5).

Figure 4 - Physic Workbench Lab Welcome page

Figure 5 - Physic Workbench Lab Welcome Page

The PWB Lab resources are available to the users for re-use in the Physics Workbench shared workspace (Figure 6) that you can access from top left links in Figure 5.

Figure 6 - Physics Workbench shared workspace.

“Easy” Workflow

The “Easy” workflow can be executed in the PWB lab using the resources available in the folder [Monoliths](#) (Figure 7).

The user can copy the query notebooks in the private workspace and execute them to retrieve temperature and salinity profiles in the Mediterranean Sea for the time period 2000-2010. They can be customized to query data in a different region and a different time period.

Some metadata variables have been selected according to the key provenance information required to any further data use. This selection can be modified according to the user needs, moreover some filters can be applied to refine the data quality, the data provider, the instrument type. Since the monoliths have the full metadata information from the source BDI, each notebook gives instructions on the reference product documentation and proper acknowledgment of the source. The notebook header reports the creators and their role in its development; please do acknowledge them, as indicated in the [Appendix](#).

The notebooks create in your workspace a folder `output` where compressed `odv` spreadsheet files are saved. These files are also already available in the shared workspace in the [output](#) folder (Figure 7). The folder [odv_collections](#) contains the examples `odv` collections to be downloaded (Figure 7) and opened with your ODV desktop.

Physics-Workbench > Monoliths

Workspace

Name	Type	Last Update	Size
monolith_argo_query.ipynb	text/plain	12 Jun 10:45 AM 2026	1.7 MB
monolith_cora_pr_query.ipynb	text/plain	12 Jun 10:45 AM 2026	992.4 kB
monolith_cora_ts_query.ipynb	text/plain	12 Jun 10:45 AM 2026	1 MB
monolith_seadatanet_query.ipynb	text/plain	17 Jun 01:10 PM 2026	828.9 kB
monolith_wod_query.ipynb	text/plain	12 Jun 10:46 AM 2026	665.2 kB
output	Public Folder	12 Jun 02:45 PM 2026	
odv_collections	Public Folder	17 Jun 12:17 PM 2026	

Figure 7 - Content of the Monoliths folder in the Physics-Workbench shared workspace.

The odv collections can also be explored directly in the PWB Lab in **webODV public dataspace** (Figure 8).

webODV Policies & Usage | webODV v2.12.22

Selected dataset: public -> PWB_EOVs_dataset_merged

eOSC | Blue-Cloud2026 public 1/3 Refresh

webODV offers online [Ocean Data View](#) services for the extraction, analysis, and visualization of oceanographic and environmental data. It is developed [Dr. Sebastian Mieruch](#) and [Prof. Dr. Reiner Schlitzer](#) at the [Alfred Wegener Institute](#).

Please cite:
 Mieruch, S. & Schlitzer, R., *BlueCloud-webODV*, <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org>, 2026.
 Please add the following sentence in the acknowledgements:
 The production of this work/product has been enabled by means of the webODV service offered via the Blue-Cloud Gateway (<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org>) operated by D4Science.org, www.d4science.org.

- BC26_workbenches
 - Eutrophication_workbench
 - Physics_workbench
 - EOVs_dataset
 - annotated
 - cleaned
 - Monoliths
 - ARGO
 - CORA_PR
 - CORA_TS
 - SEADATANET
 - WOD

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Figure 8 - Monolith collections are available for exploration in webODV public dataspace.

Pre-operational Workflow

The resources are available in the [Workflow](#) folder in the VRE (Figure 4) and they can be cloned in the personal workspace in order to execute the workflow.

Figure 9 - Pre-operational workflow resources

The PWB workflow starts from querying the data lake (Beacon merged instance) running a **jupyter notebook** that writes a parquet output file and the corresponding JSON metadata files per each BDI. The Jupyter notebook is located in [Datalake](#) (Figure 9) and in order to execute the workflow and reproduce the EOVs dataset the user needs to start the JupyterLab (see Figure 5 top bar) and open a terminal to clone the folder in the private workspace.

```
> cd /home/jovyan/workspace/
> cp -r /workspace/VREFolders/Physics-Workbench/Workflow/Datalake .
```

The folder contains three sub-folders:

```
> ls -l
auxillary_data
diagnostics
notebook
```

Select the folder `notebook` from the file browser, open the `Data_lake_query_annotation.ipynb` in the code console (Figure 10) and “Run all cells”. The executed python code will create an output folder tree in the private workspace containing the parquet and the JSON metadata files.

```
~/workspace/OUTPUT/1950_2025/DataLake
> ls -l
drwxrwxrwx 0 jovyan root 4096 Jun 22 10:10 BEACON_ARGO
drwxrwxrwx 0 jovyan root 4096 Jun 22 10:24 BEACON_CORA_PR
drwxrwxrwx 0 jovyan root 4096 Jun 22 10:45 BEACON_SEADATANET
drwxrwxrwx 0 jovyan root 4096 Jun 22 10:52 BEACON_WOD
drwxrwxrwx 0 jovyan root 4096 Jun 22 10:11 METADATA
```


Figure 10 -Screenshot of the JupyterLab session: file browser on the left and the code console on the right. In the code console is displayed the Merged Instance data query notebook

A Jupyter notebook to derive basic statistics and figures has been developed and is also provided in the directory diagnostics.

Figure 11 – Screenshot of the JupyterLab session: the code console displays the Merged Instance data diagnostics notebook.

Cloud Computing Platform (CCP)

The Cloud Computing Platform is divided into 2 main parts : the **CCP** (to execute and load methods) and the **workspace** (to load, reach, select and get outputs data).

The Physics-Workbench CCP (Figure 12) is accessible at :

<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/physics-workbench/ccp-method-execution#iss=https%3A%2F%2Faccounts.d4science.org%2Fauth%2Frealms%2Fd4science>

where the **Methods List** on the left panel comprises:

- Converting-tools → FileForge
- QC-tools → MinMax Alerts tool
- Duplicates-tools → cw Duplicates tool

Figure 12– Screenshot of the Physics-Workbench CCP method execution page.

The middle panel is the **Method execution form** that can be activated by selecting one of the available methods and clicking the “play” button (Figure 13).

Figure 13 – Screenshot of the Physics-Workbench CCP Methods List.

The **Execution Monitor** on the right panel (Figure 12) allows you to check the status of the living execution or keep track of the past ones.

MinMax Alerts Tool

The MinMax Alerts tool is available in **QC-tools** of the CCP Methods list or directly accessible at: <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/physics-workbench/ccp-method-execution?method=806bad73-815a-431d-9008-b47652263cd3>.

The [MinMax Alerts tool user guide](#) provides detailed instructions on the software and its CCP execution (Section 3). Here we describe how to reproduce the PWB execution that generated the EOVs dataset. This requires to read as input the parquet files obtained from our data lake query and available in the VRE shared workspace (Figure 9, pre-operational workflow resources), and not the ones generated by the user data lake query. In fact, due to the frequent data lake synchronization process with the source BDIs, the result of the query cannot be exactly replicated afterwards.

The **Method execution form** displayed in Figure 14 and it allows the user to select:

- the CONFIG folder containing the `config.json` file;
- the data IN folder containing the input parquet files obtained from the data lake query;
- the data REF folder containing the reference field;
- the DESTINATION folder where to put the output.

Method execution form

Minmax Alert Tool 1.42 CLEMENT WEBER

► The method adds a minmax alerting column to a set of given - argo netcdf files or - generic beacon file as input.
 3 inputs
 - data input folder (parquet files)...

Inputs

*** Runtime**
 The image of the runtime to use for method execution. This depends on the infrastructure specific protocol for interacting with registries.

*** runtime size**
 The size for a runtime to execute a method. For container based infrastructures: Small allocates up to 1 CPU and 4GB ram, medium (default) allocates up to 2 CPUs and 8G ram, large allocates up to 4 CPUs and 16Gb ram. xlarge (up to 6 CPU and 32GB ram) is available only on 'D4Science production Infrastructure with GPU'. On other infrastructures it is equivalent to large

*** select corresponding CONFIG folder - workspace protected link**

Point the minmax alerts tool config folder (containing config.json file) from your workspace

*** select data IN folder - workspace protected link**

Select the minmax alerts tool input folder (with netcdf and/or beacon parquet argo files) from your workspace

*** select data REF folder - workspace protected link**

Select the minmax alerts tool reference folder (with netcdf ref minmax fields*) from your workspace

*** select DESTINATION folder - workspace protected link**

Folder where all minmax outputs (augmented files + STATS) will be stored after minmax tool execution

Annotation
 (Optional) The value of this parameter will be associated as annotation to the execution. The default value is "yyyymmddHHMMSS"

Figure 14 – Screenshot of the Physics-Workbench CCP Methods execution form of MinMax Alert Tool.

The CONFIG and REF folders are available in the MinMax_Alerts_tool folder (Figure 15) Physics-Workbench > Workflow > MinMax_Alert_tool.

Figure 15 – Screenshot of the Physics-Workbench > Workflow > MinMax_Alert_tool.

The input parquet files are available in Physics-Workbench > Workflow > OUTPUT > 1950_2025 > Datalake (Figure 16).

Figure 16 – Screenshot of the Physics-Workbench > Workflow > OUTPUT > 1950_2025 > Datalake

Then select as the *DESTINATION folder* your private Workspace and fill the *Annotation* field to name your execution (Figure 14). Push the *Execution* button and check the Execution monitor.

Once the execution is terminated the output files will be available in the *DESTINATION folder*. Figure 17 presents several screenshots to show the user’s workspace OUTPUT folder tree, selected as the *DESTINATION folder*, generated by the MinMax Alerts tool. Per each BDI a parquet file augmented with quality information and two csv files (one for temperature and one for salinity) containing the statistics have been generated. An example of a csv file with ARGO temperature statistics is shown in Figure 18.

Please refer to the MinMax Alerts tool user guide to get detailed information on the statistics and to customize your execution.

Figure 17 - Screenshots of the OUTPUT folder selected as the DESTINATION folder for MinMax Alerts tool

```
combination,total_values_scanned,no_alert>alert_MM_already_qced>alert_MM_to_be_qced>alert_MM_QC0
BEACON_ARGO,26811319,26481061,12861,317397,0
```

Figure 18 – Statistics saved by the MinMax Alerts tool for ARGO temperature data in the csv file.

cw Duplicates Tool

The cw Duplicates tool is available in **Duplicates-tools** of the CCP Methods list, select the 32G version for reproducibility and click on the play icon to open the Method execution form.

The direct link is:

<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/physics-workbench/ccp-method-execution?method=e2cc3149-458b-411b-9faf-820a164e638a>

The [cw Duplicates tool user guide](#) provides detailed instructions on the software and its CCP execution (Section 10.4). Here we describe how to reproduce the PWB execution that generated the EOVs dataset. This requires to read as input the parquet files obtained from our data lake query and available in the VRE shared workspace (Figure 9, pre-operational workflow resources), and not the ones generated by the user data lake query. In fact, due to the frequent data lake synchronization process with the source BDIs, the result of the query cannot be exactly replicated afterwards.

The **Method execution form** displayed in Figure 17 and it allows the user to select:

- the *CONFIG folder* where is the configuration file;
- the *IN folder* where containing the input parquet files obtained from the data lake query;
- the *CACHE folder* (optional, see Section 7 of the user guide cache for its use);
- the *DESTINATION folder* where you want to store the results.

The *CONFIG folder* is Physics-Workbench > Workflow > cw_Duplicate_tool > config and it contains the cw_user_config.yaml file (Figure 19) that allows the cw Duplicate tool to look for duplicates between SEADATANET, CORA_PR and WOD within a spatial tolerance of 0.1 minutes and a temporal tolerance of 1 minute. ARGO data are not included in the duplicates scan since they have been filtered out from the other data sources within the data lake query.

```

default :
  operator :
    name : "PWB"
  output :
    filename : "EOVs_dataset"
#-----
# SOURCE INFORMATION
#-----
sources :
  - src_short_name : "PHYS_WOD"
    raw_data :
      flag : 1
      reader_type : "BEACON_PARQUET"
      data_dir : "BEACON_WOD"
      trustlevel : 3
  - src_short_name : "PHYS_SDN"
    raw_data :
      flag : 1
      reader_type : "BEACON_PARQUET"
      data_dir : "BEACON_SEADATANET"
      trustlevel : 1
  - src_short_name : "CORA"
    raw_data :
      flag : 1
      reader_type : "BEACON_PARQUET"
      data_dir : "BEACON_CORA_PR"
      trustlevel : 2
#-----
#DATA SELECTION
#-----
data_sel :
  - region : NULL
  - instr : NULL
  - groupParam : "Temperature/Salinity"
  - datatype : ["PT", "PR"]
  - period : [1950-01-01, 2026-01-01]
dupli_def :
  time_unit : "minutes"
  time_diff : 1
  pos_diff : 0.1
  instr_option : 2
  src_option : 2
  aggr_option : 4
  graph_flag : 1
removal :
  flag : 1
  group : 0
  rules_to_apply : [2,3,4,5]
    
```

Figure 19 – Screenshots of the cw_user_config.yaml file to run the cw Duplicates tool.

The input parquet files are available in Physics-Workbench > Workflow > OUTPUT > 1950_2025 > Datalake (Figure 16).

The *CACHE* folder has not been used so leave the form field empty. Once you have generated the output you could use it to execute additional tests modifying the configuration file as explained in Section 7 of the user guide.

Then select as the *DESTINATION* folder your private Workspace and fill the *Annotation* field to name your execution (Figure 20). Push the *Execution* button and check the Execution monitor.

Method execution form

CW Duplicates Tool 32G 1.2 Virginie Racape

Tool searching duplicates between n sources

Inputs

* Runtime

The image of the runtime to use for method execution. This depends on the infrastructure specific protocol for interacting with registries.

harbor.d4science.org/hub_proxy_cache/pokapok/cw-duplicates-tool:1.2

* Runtime size

The size for a runtime to execute a method. For container based infrastructures: Small allocates up to 1 CPU and 4GB ram, medium (default) allocates up to 2 CPUs and 8G ram, large allocates up to 4 CPUs and 16Gb ram. xlarge (up to 6 CPU and 32GB ram) is available only on 'D4Science production Infrastructure with GPU'. On other infrastructures it is equivalent to large

xlarge

* select CONFIG folder - workspace protected link

folder where cw_user_config.yaml is stored

select CONFIG folder - workspace protected link

* select IN folder - workspace protected link

Parent folder where in the raw beacon parquet files are stored

select IN folder - workspace protected link

(Optional) select CACHE folder - workspace protected link

cw duplicates tool cache folder (or empty folder if no available cache)

(Optional) select CACHE folder - workspace protected link

* select DESTINATION folder - workspace protected link

Folder where cw duplicates tool will be stored

select DESTINATION folder - workspace protected link

Annotation

(Optional) The value of this parameter will be associated as annotation to the execution. The default value is "yyyymmddHHMMSS"

Annotation

Figure 20 - Screenshot of the Physics-Workbench CCP Methods execution form of cw Duplicates Tool

Once the execution is terminated the output files will be available in the *DESTINATION folder*, i.e. Workspace > OUTPUT, as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21 - Screenshots of the OUTPUT folder selected as the DESTINATION folder for cw Duplicates tool

FileForge Tool

FileForge can be found in the CCP Methods list in **Converting-tools**. There are two versions: 16GB and 32GB RAM. The 32GB runs on the GPU D4S node, it has more capacities (memory and speed) but because these nodes are shared across intensive Virtual Research Environments (VREs), users may encounter brief scheduling queues if concurrency is high. Select the 16GB version to reproduce PWB EOVs dataset (Mediterranean Sea 1950-2025), open the method using the green play icon.

The direct link:

<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/physics-workbench/ccp-method-execution?method=769089f1-9afa-4879-87c7-847366d29ac6>

The [FileForge Tool user guide](#) provides detailed instructions on the software and its CCP execution (Section 4).

The **Method execution form** displayed in Figure 23 allows the user to select:

- the *Configuration File* should contain the configuration file URL (or folder URL in case of multiple configurations);
- the *Data folder* where are the **parquet files obtained from the MinMax Alert tool**;

- the *External folder* (optional, see Section 7 of the user guide cache for its use);
- the *Destination folder* where you want to store the results.

The *CONFIG folder* to select (Physics-Workbench > Workflow > FileForge > config) contains 4 configuration files (Figure 24) in order to produce the EOVS output dataset in the two versions (annotated and cleaned) and two formats (parquet and odv spreadsheet).

Figure 22 – Screenshots of the CONFIG folder to select for the FileForge tool execution: (top) in the VRE shared folder; (bottom) in the CCP method execution form.

WebODV Import and Exploration

The odv spreadsheet files, output of the Beacon queries or FileForge tool, can be explored in webODV. The zip files must be moved, opening a JupyterLab terminal, in the folder

```
/home/joyvan
```

Unzip the file

```
unzip /home/joyvan/output.zip
```

Stop the JupyterLab session from the toolbar and start webODV or click on the direct link below:

<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/physics-workbench/start-webodv>

Please refer to the webODV documentation accessible from the top bar of the webODV home page.

If you want to import your spreadsheet file, click on the Import button on the homepage top bar that launches the Import page.

Select the Import Type *Spreadsheet*:

Click on the **refresh** button on the right side of the page and Select data in the **private** dataspace.

Select the txt file and click the button **Start Import**. You can check the status of your import by clicking the **refresh** button.

Once terminated the data Import you can return to the homepage, select on the right panel the *private* dataspace and look for your file. The refresh button is always recommended. Select the file and it will appear a Service page where to click the WEBODV EXPLORE button that will open the odv collection.

8. The Physics Workbench EOVs dataset

Two versions of the EOVs dataset are created at the end of the execution, augmented by duplicates annotation and one cleaned from duplicates. Two product versions are provided: 1) *ODV spreadsheet*, and 2) *parquet* format. The aim is to serve a wide user community and multiple downstream applications. The conformity to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles is guaranteed, as also the data lineage and provenance are preserved.

ODV spreadsheet

In the odv output format all metadata are available and can be used to gather the metadata information content in terms of SOURCE_BDIs, Platform_L06, Temperature_L05, Temperature_L22, Salinity_L05, Salinity_L22, EDMO_code. MinMax Alerts tool annotation in the parquet file is read by FileForge tool and inserted in the odv spreadsheet in order to appear in webODV as additional variables (Figure 23): for each sample the minimum/maximum temperature and salinity thresholds, and the relative alert value (0 not alert, 1 alert). The alert value can be used to filter the samples jointly with the quality flags as displayed in Figure 24.

Figure 23 – Screenshot of webODV canvas with highlighted MinMax Alerts tool annotation.

Figure 24 - Screenshot of webODV sample filter pop up windows that show how to apply Quality and Range filters.

Parquet

The parquet file is annotated by the MinMax Alerts tool but the duplicates list and the list of discards from cw Duplicates tool are used by FileForge to produce the annotated and the cleaned version respectively.

All metadata are available in a JSON metadata file which is first created during the data lake (Beacon merged instance) query to avoid adding redundant data in the parquet file. The created JSON file is then integrated by FileForge with the tools versions and annotation information. This JSON metadata file, JSON-LD file compliant with the CroissantML specification, has been adopted by the experts to allow machine-to-machine data access and AI-readiness.

Dataset Analysis

The PWB EOVs dataset is made up of 1088466 profiles (Table 2, Figure 25), mainly coming from CORA_PR (50%). This result depends on the duplicate definition and decision tree applied and a further sensitivity analysis will be performed with different cw Duplicates tool configuration to better quantify it. However the user is welcome to try it and find the best solution fitting the purpose of the data usage. The [Appendix](#) presents a summary of the metadata information in the PWB EOVs dataset in terms of platforms ([L06](#)), instruments ([L05](#)), devices ([L22](#)) and data providers ([EDMO code](#)).

Figure 26 presents the data distribution map of all profiles and the ones with acceptable POSITION_QC flag (not equal to 4). The temporal distribution in Figure 27 shows a big increase after 2010 mainly due to the ARGO profiling floats profiles, which first appeared in the dataset in 2001. Even integrating the main BDIs, the Croatian, Tunisian and Libyan waters presents sparse data.

Temperature and Salinity scatter plots are shown in Figure 28 and 29 to highlight the importance of performing an additional Quality Control (QC) analysis (MinMax Alerts tool) on the integrated datasets. While ARGO and CORA data have already passed the MinMax test at the BDI level, the SeaDataNet data did not pass any automatic QC test and the WOD data QC procedure is very different. MinMax has been applied to harmonize the product data quality.

Table 3 presents a summary of the statistics computed by MinMax and provided in the form of csv files (Figure 18). Table 4 presents the main statistics that have been converted in percentages. The MinMax output csv files contain:

- total_values_scanned
- no_alert : number of observations scanned with success (no alert raised by MinMax)
- alert_MM_already_qced : number of observations with a "bad" qc that raise an alert
- alert_MM_to_be_qced : number of observation with a "good" qc that raise an alert
- alert_MM_QC0 : number of observation with QC0 that raise an alert

The MinMax raises from 1.1% (CORA) to 1.9% (WOD) of ‘bad and good’ alerts on Temperature observations and from 1.0% (SEADATANET) to 3.9% (ARGO) of ‘bad and good’ alerts on Salinity observations. Figure 30 shows the percentage of raised alerts with BAD and GOOD QC which suggest that CORA_PR presents the lowest percentages of alerts on GOOD data both for temperature and salinity, while SEADATANET and WOD have the highest ones. ARGO Temperature observations in alerts (1.2% of total) have 96% of QC flags GOOD. ARGO Salinity data instead show alerts with higher QC flags BAD percentages due to drifts observed on the floats, which are already classified as “bad” during the preprocessing step.

Table 5 presents instead the summary results of the duplicates scan from the annotated odv collection. The annotated odv collection contains 1367953 profiles, of which 845475 (62%) are unique (group 0) while the others present duplicates. ARGO profiles have no duplicates, the 64% of CORA_PR, 57% of SEADATANET and 51% of WOD profiles are unique. These percentages, determined by the detection of the “exact duplicates” are reasonable to our knowledge. However, further sensitivity analysis will be performed for the future releases.

SOURCE_BDI	Profiles	%
BEACON_CORA_PR	549249	50.5%
BEACON_WOD	265740	24.4%
BEACON_SEADATANET	171686	15.8%
BEACON_ARGO	101771	9.3%
TOTAL	1088446	

Table 2 – Number of stations per BDI in the PWB EOVS dataset and their relative percentage (cleaned version).

Figure 25 - Percentage of profiles per SOURCE_BDI in the cleaned PWB EOVS dataset.

Figure 26 – Data distribution map of the cleaned PWB EOVS dataset: (top) all stations (1088446 profiles) ; (bottom) stations with position_qc (not eq 4) not BAD (1085347 profiles)

Figure 27 - Temporal distribution map of the cleaned PWB EOVS dataset from webODV: a) annual; b) seasonal.

Figure 28 – Temperature scatter plot of cleaned PWB EOVS dataset: a) all measurements; b) GOOD or PROBABLY GOOD depth and temperature measurements; c) GOOD or PROBABLY GOOD depth and temperature measurements with temperature alert 0.

Figure 29 – Salinity scatter plot of PWB EOVS dataset: a) all measurements; b) GOOD or PROBABLY GOOD depth and salinity measurements; c) GOOD or PROBABLY GOOD depth and salinity measurements with salinity alert 0.

TEMPERATURE	tot values scanned	no alert	alert with BAD QC	alert with GOOD QC
BEACON_ARGO	26811319	26481061	12861	317397
BEACON_CORA_PR	147244904	145624870	808143	811891
BEACON_SEADATANET	40519404	39920034	121194	478176
BEACON_WOD	59211187	58074125	333215	803847
SALINITY				
BEACON_ARGO	26811319	25765532	776477	269310
BEACON_CORA_PR	147244909	145505350	614979	1124580
BEACON_SEADATANET	41262972	40842043	29233	391696
BEACON_WOD	59211187	58158072	27429	1025686

Table 3 – MinMax statistics per BDI for the PWB EOVs dataset.

TEMPERATURE	no alert	alert	alert with BAD QC	alert with GOOD QC
BEACON_ARGO	98,8%	1,2%	3,9%	96,1%
BEACON_CORA_PR	98,9%	1,1%	49,9%	50,1%
BEACON_SEADATANET	98,5%	1,5%	20,2%	79,8%
BEACON_WOD	98,1%	1,9%	29,3%	70,7%
SALINITY				
BEACON_ARGO	96,1%	3,9%	74,2%	25,8%
BEACON_CORA_PR	98,8%	1,2%	35,4%	64,6%
BEACON_SEADATANET	99,0%	1,0%	6,9%	93,1%
BEACON_WOD	98,2%	1,8%	2,6%	97,4%

Table 4 – Alerts statistics in percentages per BDI for the PWB EOVs dataset.

Figure 30 – Percentages of raised alerts with BAD QC and GOOD QC per each BDI.

TEMPERATURE	Profiles	in group 0	in a duplicate group
BEACON_ARGO	101771	101771(100%)	
BEACON_CORA_PR	652734	419867 (64%)	232867 (36%)
BEACON_SEADATANET	185446	106007 (57%)	79439 (43%)
BEACON_WOD	428002	217830 (51%)	210172 (49%)
TOTAL in annotated	1367953	845475	522478
TOTAL in cleaned	1088446		
	279507		

Table 5 – Duplicates statistics per BDI from the annotated PWB EOVS dataset.

PWB EOVS dataset re-usability

The PWB Lab pilot implementation generated the first version of the PWB EOVS dataset. As mentioned earlier, this added value and ready to use product is provided in both odv and parquet formats to serve different user communities. In specific, the odv collections, in the annotated and cleaned versions, can be directly explored by the users in the public [webODV](#) dataspace on D4Science.

Due to the complexity and intrinsic temporal, spatial, platform variability of the metadata information associated with temperature and salinity observations, the duplicates detection cannot be perfect, even though a significant number of duplicates have been identified and removed using the CW Duplicate tool. However all efforts have been put into ensuring: data integrity and consistency from the source BDI to the BC2026 data lake, data traceability and workflow replicability, preserving provenance information.

The PWB team provides here after some suggestions:

- to use the alerts annotation joint with the source BDI quality flags to understand how to best use the data;
- to use the duplicates group and discard rule number to verify in the annotated version the detected duplicates;
- to use the webODV duplicate scan tool to verify the remaining duplicates, analyze them and decide how to treat them according to the intended use;
- to acknowledge the BDI data sources whenever using the BC2026 data lake and the PWB EOVS dataset;
- to share with us your concerns;
- to consult the PWB team for proper data usage.

Whenever you use the PWB resources (listed in the [Annex](#)) in your research, do not forget to properly cite them (both data and tools) and acknowledge the [Physics Workbench Lab](#) Team.

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Appendix

Physics Workbench Lab resources published in the BC2026 Catalog

All resources

<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/physics-workbench/catalogue>

Physics Workbench Lab service

S. Simoncelli, C. Coatanoan, M. Couppey, C. Fratianni, J. Gourrion, S. Iona, G. Moncoiffe, R. Kooyman, S. Mieruch, V. Racapé, A. Sizun, T. Szekely, C. Weber, M. Vernet - Physics Workbench Lab. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026.

https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/physics_workbench_lab

Beacon Monoliths

R. Kooyman. Beacon - ARGO. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026. <https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCNodeDTO-Catalogue/beacon - argo>

R. Kooyman. Beacon - SeaDataNet CDI. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026.

<https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCNodeDTO-Catalogue/beacon - seadatanet cdi>

R. Kooyman. Beacon - CORA-PR. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026.

https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCNodeDTO-Catalogue/beacon_cora-pr

R. Kooyman. Beacon - CORA-TS. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026.

https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCNodeDTO-Catalogue/beacon_cora-ts

R. Kooyman. Beacon - World Ocean Database. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026.

https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCNodeDTO-Catalogue/beacon - world_ocean_database

Monoliths query notebooks

Kooyman, R., Krijger, T., Coatanoan, C., Simoncelli, S. Argo data query. Blue-Cloud Jupyter Notebook, 2026.

https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/argo_data_query

Kooyman, R., Krijger, T., Simoncelli, S. SeaDataNet data query. Blue-Cloud Jupyter Notebook, 2026.

https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/seadatanet_data_query

Kooyman, R., Krijger, T., Simoncelli, S. CORA_PR (Copernicus Marine Service product) data (profiles) query. Blue-Cloud Jupyter Notebook, 2026. https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/cora_pr_copernicus_marine_service_product_data_profiles_query

https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/cora_pr_copernicus_marine_service_product_data_profiles_query

Kooyman, R., Krijger, T., Simoncelli, S. CORA_TS (Copernicus Marine Service product) data (time series) query. Blue-Cloud Jupyter Notebook, 2026. https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/cora_ts_copernicus_marine_service_product_data_query

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Monoliths example datasets

Simoncelli, S. Monoliths output datasets: Mediterranean Sea 2000-2010. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026. https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/example_output_datasets_mediterranean_sea_2000-2010

Beacon Merged Instance (Physics Workbench data lake)

R. Kooyman. Beacon - Beacon - Merged T&S. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026. https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCNodeDTO-Catalogue/beacon_-_merged_t_s

Physics Workbench data lake query

Kooyman, R., Krijger, T., Simoncelli, S., Fratianni, C., Coatanoan, C., Szekely, T., Iona, A., Moncoiffé, G. Physics Workbench data lake query. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026. https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/physics_workbench_data_lake_query

webODV

Mieruch, S. webODV service. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026. https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/webodv_in_physics-workbench

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Racapé, V. MinMax tool in Physics Workbench. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026. https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/minmax_alerts_tool_deployed_on_physical_workbench

cw Duplicates tool

Racapé, V. cw Duplicates tool in Physics Workbench. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026. https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/cw_duplicate_detection_tool_deployed_on_physical_workbench

FileForge tool

Coupey, M. *FileForge tool in Physics Workbench Cloud Computing Platform. Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026.*

https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/fileforge_on_physics_workbench_ccp

EOVs Dataset

Simoncelli, S., Coatanoan, C., Coupey, M., Fratianni, C., Gourrion, J., Iona, A., Kooyman, R., Moncoiffé, G., Mieruch, S., Racapé, V., Sizun, A., Szekely, T., Weber, C. *Physics Workbench EOVs dataset Blue-Cloud Infrastructure, 2026.*

https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Physics-Workbench/physics_eovs_dataset

EOVs Dataset Metadata statistics

Table A – Number of stations per PLATFORM (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/>) in the PWB EOVs dataset (cleaned version).

Platforms	Counts
SDN:L06::27	396409
SDN:L06::30	281048
(empty)	136151
SDN:L06::46	101771
SDN:L06::31	57592
SDN:L06::39	31037
SDN:L06::32	14425
SDN:L06::36	7096
SDN:L06::0	5778
SDN:L06::26	1384
SDN:L06::70	1298
SDN:L06::35	1219
SDN:L06::33	1177
SDN:L06::34	32
SDN:L06::3D	16
SDN:L06::37	6
SDN:L06::16	5

Table B – Number of temperature and salinity profiles per INSTRUMENT
 (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/current/>) in the PWB EOVS dataset (cleaned version).

TEMPERATURE_L05	Counts	SALINITY_L05	Counts
SDN:L05::134	410159	SDN:L05::134	408792
SDN:L05::130	213564	SDN:L05::130	213372
SDN:L05::132	139237	(empty)	207693
SDN:L05::30	117194	SDN:L05::30	117194
(empty)	100275	SDN:L05::132	78111
SDN:L05::390	12123	SDN:L05::389	42947
SDN:L05::389	8765	SDN:L05::390	12123
SDN:L05::350	6391	SDN:L05::350	6391
SDN:L05::999	914	SDN:L05::999	914
SDN:L05::113	806	SDN:L05::113	806
SDN:L05::351	69	SDN:L05::351	69
SDN:L05::355	28	SDN:L05::135	26
SDN:L05::135	26	SDN:L05::354	8
SDN:L05::354	10		

Table C – Number of temperature and salinity profiles per DEVICES
 (https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L22/current/) in the PWB EOVS dataset (cleaned version).

Values	Counts	Values	Counts
SDN:L22::TOOL0001	506239	SDN:L22::TOOL0001	504872
(empty)	338367	SDN:L22::TOOL1287	50698
SDN:L22::TOOL1291	66412	(empty)	49895
SDN:L22::TOOL1287	62821	SDN:L22::TOOL0669	22142
SDN:L22::TOOL0435	52446	SDN:L22::TOOL1026	6263
SDN:L22::TOOL0669	22334	SDN:L22::TOOL0058	1563
SDN:L22::TOOL0263	17744	SDN:L22::TOOL0435	1086
SDN:L22::TOOL1026	6263	SDN:L22::TOOL0715	718
SDN:L22::TOOL0718	3467	SDN:L22::TOOL1745	317
SDN:L22::TOOL0262	2056	SDN:L22::TOOL0035	293
SDN:L22::TOOL0058	1711	SDN:L22::TOOL0412	228
SDN:L22::TOOL0717	682	SDN:L22::TOOL0042	227
SDN:L22::TOOL0715	592	SDN:L22::TOOL0047	185
SDN:L22::TOOL1745	317	SDN:L22::TOOL0040	169
SDN:L22::TOOL0035	293	SDN:L22::TOOL0262	103
SDN:L22::TOOL0042	227	SDN:L22::TOOL0592	99
SDN:L22::TOOL0713	226	SDN:L22::TOOL0718	98
SDN:L22::TOOL0047	185	SDN:L22::TOOL0002	97
SDN:L22::TOOL0040	169	SDN:L22::TOOL0149	94
SDN:L22::TOOL0592	101	SDN:L22::TOOL0417	78
SDN:L22::TOOL0002	97	SDN:L22::TOOL1291	63
SDN:L22::TOOL0149	94	SDN:L22::TOOL1508	48
SDN:L22::TOOL0640	94	SDN:L22::TOOL0591	28
SDN:L22::TOOL1508	48	SDN:L22::TOOL0242	16
SDN:L22::TOOL1383	33	SDN:L22::TOOL0213	10

SDN:L22::TOOL0591	29	SDN:L22::TOOL0714	1
SDN:L22::TOOL0451	28		
SDN:L22::TOOL1290	23		
SDN:L22::TOOL0213	10		
SDN:L22::TOOL0412	7		
SDN:L22::TOOL1386	2		
SDN:L22::TOOL0714	1		

Table D – Number of temperature and salinity profiles per EDMO_CODE (data provider, <https://edmo.seadatanet.org/>) in the PWB EOVS dataset (cleaned version).

EDMO_CODE	Counts
1051	236988
3410	182996
1944	72967
120	65295
1054	63792
1441	60582
486	39477
4514	18174
2895	17709
144	16809
490	16586
164	16454
494	16448
26	15478
696	13769
353	11143

3577	10601
5241	10022
963	8783
2881	7677
17	7261
136	7232
540	6862
931	6555
1130	3965
992	3858
108	3518
515	3477
1338	3116
1979	2607
1835 681	2579
134	2535
269	2479
2391	2455
2842	2355
952	2287
1850	2212
753 1056 120 134	2178
4614	1903
957	1887
3844	1772
2947	1751
5922	1681
3009	1668

700	1639
150	1608
2432	1484
127	1435
3078	1427
353 486 396 43	1141
(empty)	1094
1015	1063
1799	1043
702	947
1009	911
590	773
234	763
6177	754
1053 727	646
238	643
43	636
840	589
237	576
520	553
711	549
5041	542
630	529
96 3234 353 43	519
1351	501
1363	482
5115	474
280	461

440	447
681	443
791	413
1053 681	407
1384	405
1507	399
353 43	365
126	362
3839	346
721	346
3234 353 396 43	344
2431	332
1004	327
685	302
731	288
1461	272
513	269
44	240
574	234
963 120	228
1043	220
1232	213
708	206
1020	195
3639	188
730	188
4748	180
96 3234	173

149	171
4640	171
682	166
1167	144
353 120	136
145	134
902	133
1393	130
1485	129
2489	129
709	128
544	127
1941	123
4755	119
691	107
269 963 120	105
269 120	96
802	95
96	92
3928	84
128	75
1390	75
29	74
727	73
532	72
5801	69
1838	67
549	65

1433	63
3926	57
487	55
5709	55
227	48
1409	47
900	47
903	45
756	42
1578	40
129	39
1946	39
1088	33
4588	33
138	32
819	32
5787	27
2002	26
2295	25
4606	24
1778	23
3936	23
552	22
396	21
1084	19
47	18
302	16
560	16

527	14
723	12
1842	8
1888	8
2919	8
3945	7
4537	7
946	6
1016	4
1537	4
1942	4
2516	4
3234	4
1440	3
485	3
3433	2
501	2
5231	2
1052	1
1484	1
1811	1
2279	1
3587	1
838	1

Project Title	Blue-Cloud 2026: A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters
Project Acronym	Blue-Cloud 2026
Project Number	101094227
Type of project	RIA – Research and Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
Starting date of Project	01 January 2023
Duration of the project	42 months
Website	www.blue-cloud.org

Eutrophication Workbench Virtual Laboratory Users handbook

Work Package	WP3 Developing and testing analytical Blue Cloud workbenches for generating highly qualified data collections (Essential Ocean Variables, EOVS)
Task	T3.3 EOVS workbench for eutrophication: chlorophyll, nutrients, oxygen
Lead author	Catalina Reyes (OGS, https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3906-471X)
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Peer reviewers	Dick Schaap (MARIS), Massimiliano Assante (CNR)
Version	V1.5
Due Date	30/06/2026
Submission Date	30/06/2026

Dissemination Level

x	PU: Public
	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	23/03/2026	Catalina Reyes (OGS)	Updated v1.0
0.2	11/06/2026	all partners	Updated v1.2
0.3	13/06/2026	Catalina Reyes (OGS)	move comments from the master file to the final file. converted to google docs to add codeblock and zotero for references.
0.4	15/06/2026	Gwen Moncoiffe (BODC)	Extended the section: harmonization and standardization.
0.5	19/06/2026	Julie Gatti, Virginie Recape	Comments to the recommendations section.
0.6	25/06/2026	Dick Schaap (MARIS), Massimiliano Assante (CNR)	Review
1.5	29/06/2026	Catalina Reyes (OGS)	Final version for submission

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
BDI	Blue Data Infrastructures
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
EWB	Eutrophication workbench
NVS	NERC Vocabulary Server
VLab	Virtual Laboratory

Keywords

EOSC; V Labs; Big Data; Virtual Research Environment; Data infrastructures

Disclaimer

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1. Introduction

The Eutrophication Workbench Virtual Laboratory (EWB VLab) is a cloud-based environment developed in the D4Science e-infrastructure within the Blue-Cloud 2026 project that enables access to and harmonized use of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) relevant to marine eutrophication. It integrates in-situ data from major Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs) such as the Copernicus Marine Service, EMODnet Chemistry, and the World Ocean Database.

This User's Manual provides a technical description of the workbench, its services, data access procedures, and recommended workflows. It is addressed to scientists, data managers, and policy makers and advisors who wish to merge, validate, and analyze EOVS collections for eutrophication assessment.

2. Scope and objectives

The Eutrophication Workbench aims to:

- Provide a common and customisable, cloud-based workflow for merging, aggregating, and harmonizing multi-source datasets managed by different BDIs.
- Produce validated, customizable EOVS collections for chlorophyll-a, nutrients (nitrate, nitrite+nitrate, ammonium, phosphate, silicate), and dissolved oxygen based on the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) recommendations.
- Enable transparent, reproducible data preparation suitable for indicator derivation and regional eutrophication assessments.

The workbench is not a modelling or forecasting environment; it focuses on in-situ data harmonization and standardization, quality control, and exploratory analysis.

3. Blue Data Infrastructures and Essential Ocean Variables

To ensure global scientific relevance, data interoperability, and methodological rigor, the Eutrophication Workbench aligns its data architecture with the internationally recognized framework established by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS). Following the guidelines detailed in "GOOS Essential Ocean Variables: the backbone of a sustained and evolving global ocean observing system" (Martín Míguez et al., 2026), the workbench prioritizes a specific subset of Biogeochemical EOVS that are critical for identifying, monitoring, and analyzing marine eutrophication.

The core EOVs accessible through the Eutrophication Workbench include:

- **Ocean color / Phytoplankton biomass (Proxy: Chlorophyll-a):** Used to monitor primary production, algal blooms, and ecological shifts resulting from nutrient enrichment.
- **Oxygen:** Specifically dissolved oxygen, essential for assessing water column ventilation, tracking oxygen depletion, and identifying hypoxic or anoxic "dead" zones.
- **Nutrients:** The foundational drivers of eutrophication. The workbench aggregates and harmonizes data for the following specific macro-nutrients: Nitrate (NO₃), Nitrite + Nitrate (NO₂ + NO₃), Ammonium (NH₄), Phosphate (PO₄) and Silicate (SiO₄).

The EWB acts as a federated data lake engine, harvesting and synthesizing raw datasets from three primary **Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs)**:

1. **Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS):** Utilizing the *in situ* Component thematic assembly center to acquire delayed-mode, highly qualified, historically aggregated, and regionally validated marine datasets for operational oceanography data across European seas.
2. **EMODnet Chemistry:** Providing highly qualified, historically aggregated, and regionally validated marine datasets from European regional seas.
3. **World Ocean Database (WOD):** Maintained by NOAA, serving as the world's largest publicly available archive of global ocean data to provide broader geographic coverage.

4. Metadata standards and controlled vocabularies

The core challenge of multi-source integration is data heterogeneity. To eliminate ambiguity when combining assets from CMEMS, EMODnet, and WOD, the workbench enforces strict data syntax and semantic interoperability rules. Metadata standards and controlled vocabularies are dynamically mapped during the ingestion phase. This ensures that regardless of an asset's origin, variables are unified under a singular, standardized vocabulary, allowing users to safely perform cross-infrastructure comparative analyses.

This is based on a list of essential metadata which was defined by experts and that subsequently were mapped to obtain the merged dataset.

5. Accessing the workbench

To interact with the data collections, analytical notebooks, and processing engines, users must first access the EWB VLab environment upon registration on the D4Science e-infrastructure. The workbench is embedded within the broader European open science ecosystem and can be reached via three distinct entry paths, depending on whether you are executing workflows, exploring the service catalog, or accessing via federated European infrastructure.

5.1. Entry points

	Purpose	Primary URL / Registry
Blue-Cloud Gateway - Eutrophication workbench	Interactive execution of tools, workspace access, and notebook environment.	https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/eutrophication-workbench
Blue-Cloud Catalogue	Service discovery, metadata inspection, and social sharing of the VLab asset.	https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/eutrophication-workbench/catalogue

Table 1 – EWB VLab entry points

5.2. Authentication and authorization

Access to the Eutrophication Workbench Virtual Laboratory is secured via a centralized Identity and Access Management (IAM) framework managed by D4Science. This ensures data security, fine-grained access control and auditability of user interactions with the platform.

Users can authenticate using the D4Science Single Sign-On (SSO) service, which supports federated identity providers. You do not need to create a unique credential set if you belong to a participating institution.

Supported authentication paths include:

- **Institutional Credentials (eduGAIN):** Allows researchers to log in using their primary university or research center credentials via the global eduGAIN federation.
- **Social & Developer Identities:** Supports authentication via authenticated third-party accounts, including ORCID, GitHub, and Google.
- **Native Blue-Cloud/D4Science Accounts:** Users without federated institutional access can register for a direct, native account on the D4Science platform.

Figure 1 – Blue cloud gateway sign in.

5.2.1. Authorization and VRE membership (access control)

Authentication verifies who you are, while authorization determines what you can do. The EWB operates an open but moderated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) to manage computing resources effectively.

Upon first login, users must **request access** to the EWB VLab via the gateway interface. Once the VRE administrators approve the request, the user account is assigned to a VRE group either Vlab Developers or Vlab End Users.

Once fully authorized, users are granted the following capabilities within the environment:

- **Execute analytical notebooks:** Full permissions to spawn personal JupyterHub instances pre-configured with the computational environment and the beacon-py SDK required to query the data lake.
- **Run cloud computing methods:** Access to the D4Science **CCP** execution tab to configure and launch the CW Duplicates Tool and FileForge engine.

- **Workspace storage and collaboration:** Secure allocation of cloud storage within the VRE Workspace. Users can save filtered Parquet subsets, write intermediate duplicate data reports, and directly share data assets securely with other members of the consortium.

5.2.2. API Tokens for external and notebook access

For programmatic access to the Beacon data lake engine via external Python scripts or internal Jupyter Notebooks, standard browser authentication is insufficient. Users must generate a **Personal Access Token** (<https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/eutrophication-workbench/authorization-how-to>) from the EWB VLab dashboard (Figure 3). This token must be passed securely into your initialization scripts (e.g., `client = Client(BEACON_INSTANCE_URL, token=YOUR_TOKEN)`) to authenticate data extraction queries or to explore the swagger service (the latter only available for the maris endpoint).

Figure 2 – API token access for the beacon D4Science instance.

6. System architecture and deployment

The EWB VLab is built upon a modular, distributed system architecture designed to handle large-scale marine biogeochemical data. Rather than operating as a rigid, monolithic system, the workbench implements an end-to-end processing workflow (Figure 3) consisting of four core components: **Beacon**, the **CW Duplicates Tool**, **FileForge**, and **webODV**.

Figure 3 – Conceptual architectural workflow and data progression within the Eutrophication Workbench.

6.1. Beacon data lake

6.1.1. Overview

Beacon is an open-source data lake query engine designed to make large collections of scientific data files directly, easily, and quickly queryable. It focuses primarily on environmental and observational datasets such as oceanographic and climate data but is extendible and proven to work well for other domains as well, as long as the input data follows any standard-like way of describing its contents. Users can request subsets by filtering variables, time ranges, spatial regions, or metadata attributes, and Beacon automatically retrieves and harmonizes the relevant data across all matching files.

In January 2025, Beacon 1.0.0 was made publicly available as an open-source software, allowing everyone to set-up their own Beacon node to enhance the access to their data or use existing Beacon nodes from well-known data infrastructures such as Euro-Argo or the World Ocean Database (WOD) for fast and easy access to harmonized data subsets. More technical details, example applications, GitHub code, and general information on Beacon can be found on the website (<https://beacon-datalake.org/>).

Within the EWB workflow, Beacon acts as the data ingestion and harmonization layer. Instead of requiring users to manually download and cross-reference big data archives from various Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs), Beacon allows users to request highly specific subsets.

Users can apply dynamic filters based on:

- Specific Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)
- Temporal ranges (dates)
- Spatial regions (bounding boxes or geographical polygons)
- Specific metadata attributes

Beacon automatically executes these queries across the data lake, retrieves the relevant files, and harmonizes data and metadata schemas into a unified, high-performance structured format in real time.

6.1.2. Eutrophication workbench (EWB) beacon instances

To facilitate flexible, high-performance data exploration, the Eutrophication Workbench deploys Beacon instances across two structural tiers: Infrastructure-Specific (**Monolithic**) Nodes and Federated (**Merged**) Nodes.

These nodes are natively hosted and cross-mirrored between MARIS and the D4Science Cloud Platform, providing data redundancy and high availability. Users can interact with these endpoints directly through pre-configured Jupyter Notebooks within the EWB VLab.

6.1.2.1. Monolithic (infrastructure-specific) beacon instances

Monolithic instances isolate individual Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs) into distinct, dedicated query engines. These nodes are optimized for targeted queries where a researcher needs to inspect, evaluate, or extract data from a single specific institutional authority without cross-contamination from other networks.

Using monolithic instances is highly recommended during the initial exploration phases, for validating data provenance, or when performing comparative studies between different source infrastructures.

Blue Data Infrastructure	Source Dataset & Collection Criteria	Beacon MARIS Endpoint	Beacon D4Science Endpoint	Blue cloud/EOSCnodeDTO catalogue entry
World Ocean Database (WOD)	Actual depth profiles, harvested directly from NCEI/NOAA (ncei.noaa.gov).	beacon-wod.maris.nl	beacon-wod.d4science.org	https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCNodeDTO-Catalogue/beacon-world_ocean_database
EMODnet Chemistry	Highly qualified EMODnet	beacon-emodchem.maris.nl	beacon-emodnet-	https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCNodeDTO-

	Chemistry Collection (v2025), retrieved from WebODV.		chemistry.d4science.org	Catalogue/beacon - emodnet_chemistry
Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS)	Biogeochemical (BGC) discrete in situ datasets: INSITU_GLO_BGC_DISCRETE_MY_013_046	beacon-cmems.maris.nl	beacon-bgc.d4science.org	https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCNodeDTO-Catalogue/beacon - cmems_bgc

Table 2 – Overview of deployed monolithic Beacon instances

6.1.2.2. Federated (merged) beacon instances

Going beyond individual repository isolation, the Eutrophication Workbench demonstrates true cloud-native data federation by combining the data pipelines of all three monolithic sources into a unified, cross-infrastructure network layer.

The **Merged beacon instance** aggregates the contents of the WOD, EMODnet Chemistry, and CMEMS BGC repositories into a singular queryable node. Instead of writing multiple query blocks and manually appending separate datasets, a user can broadcast a single spatial-temporal query to the merged node. The engine processes the request globally across all three underlying collections and outputs a unified dataset in the desired format, for example Apache Parquet (see the supported formats section at: <https://maris-development.github.io/beacon/>).

Combined Federated Collections	Beacon MARIS Endpoint	Beacon D4Science Endpoint	Blue cloud/EOSCnodeDTO catalogue entry
EMODnet Chemistry, WOD, CMEMS BGC	beacon-wb2-eutrophication.maris.nl	beacon-wb2-eutrophication.d4science.org	https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/EOSCNodeDTO-Catalogue/beacon - merged_eutrophication

Table 3 – Overview EWB merged Beacon instance.

⚠ Important data processing note: Because the merged beacon instance represents an absolute aggregation of overlapping data infrastructures, the raw output datasets will contain spatial and temporal observation duplicates. This merged dataset is designed to serve as the direct upstream input file for the CW Duplicates Tool (see Section 4.2), which identifies duplicate artifacts before analysis.

6.1.3. Accessing beacon via a Jupyter Notebook

Programmatic interaction with any deployed Beacon endpoint (detailed in Section 6.1.2) is driven by the **Beacon API**. Rather than forcing researchers to write raw HTTP REST requests manually, the EWB VLab leverages a native, purpose-built library: the Beacon Python Software Development Kit (SDK).

6.1.3.1. SDK core resources and repositories

- Production source code and library: <https://github.com/maris-development/beacon-py>
- Official EWB template and workflow Notebooks: https://github.com/maris-development/beacon-blue-cloud/tree/EutrophicationWorkbench_CR/notebook-examples/EutrophicationWorkbenchVLab

6.1.3.2. Step-by-step implementation guide

To construct a notebook workflow that extracts harmonized subsets directly from the data lake, users follow a structured four-stage execution pipeline:

1. **Environmental setup and client initialization:** First, ensure the environment has the SDK installed (`pip install beacon_api`). In your notebook, import the client modules and establish an authenticated connection to the targeted Beacon endpoint (e.g., the World Ocean Database node). You must pass your personal D4Science Access Token to clear the security layer.
2. **Defining multi-dimensional query criteria:** Queries to the data lake engine are highly targeted to prevent memory bottlenecks. The SDK exposes an abstraction layer to filter data collections across four primary dimensions:
 - a. **Variables:** Specifying target parameters using vocabulary-controlled keys depending on the queried beacon instance (e.g., `COMMON_OXYGEN` in the merged or `Water body nitrate` in the EMODnet chemistry monolithic instance).
 - b. **Spatial bounding box:** Constraining the search space using geographic coordinates (`min_lon`, `max_lon`, `min_lat`, `max_lat`).
 - c. **Temporal interval:** Defining the exact chronological boundaries (`start_date`, `end_date`).
 - d. **Metadata property matrices:** Narrowing the scope further based on infrastructure-specific criteria like asset platform type (e.g., *moored buoy*, *towed CTD*) or data originating research institutes (e.g., *EDMO code*).
3. **Query submission and data stream assimilation:** Once compiled, the query object is transmitted via the SDK to the remote Beacon engine. The engine transparently parses the target (e.g. Apache Parquet) files across the distributed data lake, applies your masks, aggregates the matching indices, and prepares the downstream delivery bundle.

To maximize the transparency and reproducible nature of marine data integration within the Eutrophication Workbench, the reference implementation for querying the EMODnet Chemistry monolithic instance is published openly as a production-ready Jupyter Notebook.

6.1.3.3. Practical python code blueprint

Below is the concrete, production-grade Python implementation extracted from the official [EMODnet Chemistry monolithic BEACON query notebook](#) (Reyes Suarez, 2026a). This blueprint establishes a client connection, configures explicit column selections with interoperable aliases, applies strict spatiotemporal and quality filters, and fetches the data directly into an analytical structure.

```
# =====
# BLUE-CLOUD 2026: EUTROPHICATION WORKBENCH VIRTUAL LABORATORY
# Practical Python Code Blueprint: Querying EMODnet Chemistry via Monolithic BEACON
# =====

from beacon_api import * # Import the Beacon API client

TOKEN = os.getenv('D4SCIENCE_TOKEN') # This will fetch the token from the VRE environment.
print("Initializing connection to the EMODnet Chemistry monolithic Beacon node..")

# Define the target Monolithic Beacon Endpoint URI
BEACON_INSTANCE_URL = "https://beacon-emodnet-chemistry.d4science.org"

# Instantiate the Beacon Client
emodnet_client = Client('https://beacon-emodnet-chemistry.d4science.org', jwt_token=TOKEN)

print(f"Successfully connected to endpoint: {BEACON_INSTANCE_URL}")

# Initialize the Step-by-Step Query Builder
query_builder = client.query()

print("\nConfiguring structural metadata and tracking columns..")
# Select core identifier and institutional metadata columns
query_builder.add_select_column("Originator")
query_builder.add_select_column("LOCAL_CDI_ID")
query_builder.add_select_column("EDMO_code")

# Select primary spatial vertical context dimensions
query_builder.add_select_column("yyyy-mm-ddThh:mm:ss.sss", alias="time")
query_builder.add_select_column("Latitude", alias="latitude")
query_builder.add_select_column("Longitude", alias="longitude")
query_builder.add_select_column("Depth", alias="depth")

# -----
# PARAMETER SELECTION EXAMPLES
```

```
# -----
query_builder.add_select_column("Water body chlorophyll-a", alias="Water body chlorophyll-
a")
query_builder.add_select_column("Water body chlorophyll-a_qc", alias="Water body
chlorophyll-a_qc")

print("\nApplying spatiotemporal constraints and quality filters...")
# Define bounding criteria (Modify constraints based on regional focus)
query_builder.add_range_filter("TIME", "2010-01-01T00:00:00", "2024-12-31T23:59:59") #
Temporal range
query_builder.add_range_filter("LATITUDE", 30.0, 46.0) #
Mediterranean example bounding box
query_builder.add_range_filter("LONGITUDE", -6.0, 36.0) #
Mediterranean example bounding box
query_builder.add_range_filter("DEPTH", 0.0, 250.0) #
Euphotic/epipelagic zone limit

# Execute query to fetch the harmonized dataset from the data lake
print("Submitting query and executing remote server aggregation...")
df = query_builder.to_pandas_dataframe()

print(f"\nData extraction completed successfully!")

print("\nFirst 5 rows of the FAIR-harmonized DataFrame:")
print(df.head())
# Download in parquet format
query_builder.to_parquet()
```

6.1.4. Harmonization and standardization

The harmonisation and standardisation effort within Blue-Cloud2026 aims at enabling faster integration, more accurate duplicate checks, and greater interoperability while minimising information loss and maintaining traceability.

It was applied to the diverse unit, coordinate reference system, time format and quality flag conventions used across the source BDIs, as well as the different labelling conventions used for variable names, observation platforms, sensors and sampling devices.

The general approach to standardisation and semantic harmonisation within the Blue-Cloud2026 project is described in a number of Deliverables (e.g. [D3.1](#) and [D5.5](#)). In this section, we will focus on information related to the practical implementation of semantic harmonisation for the EWB.

The strategy and rules followed for the semantic harmonisation are as follows:

6.1.4.1. Parameters

The BODC P01 Parameter Usage Vocabulary (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/>) was the only parameter naming vocabulary capable of accommodating the range of variable naming practices in use in the different source BDIs. Using either SKOS mappings stored in the NVS, or mappings hardcoded in Beacon, source parameter labels were matched to their exact or closest broader P01 parameter concept based on knowledge of what these labels represented.

CMEMS BGC: the P09 MEDATLAS Parameter Usage Vocabulary (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P09/>) used by CMEMS for parameter labelling are already matched to their respective P01 concepts by the P09 governance team at Ifremer hence these mappings were already available from the NVS.

EMODnet Chemistry: the P35 EMODnet Chemistry aggregated parameter names (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P35/>) used by EMODnet Chemistry for their aggregated data products were matched to their equivalent P01 concept. These one-to-one mappings are different from the ones already present in the NVS. The latter are needed for the dynamic harvesting of data from SeaDataNet to EMODnet Chemistry. In order to avoid the risk of disrupting the existing workflow, the Blue-Cloud mappings were hardcoded in Beacon.

WOD: uses its own internal codelists (published in the WOD Manual and web pages). These were mapped manually to P01 codes and stored in Beacon.

6.1.4.2. Units

Source units and their labels were standardised using the NVS P06 vocabulary (<https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P06/current/>).

Source units are read by Beacon and mapped to their matching concept from the NVS P06 vocabulary uniquely identified in Beacon by its URN (e.g. SDN:P06::KGUM or SDN:P06::UPOX) and preferred labels.

6.1.4.3. Platforms

The common vocabulary used for platform harmonisation was the NVS L06 SeaVoX Platform Categories vocabulary (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/>). However duplicate record identification across all BDIs but Argo, also benefitted from having not only the platform type but also the platform instance accurately identified. This was done by mapping all non-Argo platform instances to the ICES platform code vocabulary using their NVS C17 unique URN (e.g.

SDN:C17::74E3). Different methods had to be followed to map the source information from the various BDIs to their correct C17 code. Below is a summary of the different approaches.

CMEMS: values in “ship_platform_number” are matched to the call-sign in C17. Beacon uses the time at which the observation was made to ensure that the call-sign is matched to the correct platform instance in the C17 vocabulary. L06 platform type URNs are derived from the CMEMS Data Type Bigram with a conditional criteria based on the value of the WMO_instrument_type.

EMODnet chemistry: the C17 platform instance and/or L06 platform type are extracted from the CDI metadata record and directly inserted in their appropriate fields in Beacon.

WOD: WOD maintains its own list of codes and names for platform instances¹. The WOD list was extracted and manually mapped to C17 concepts using a series of iterative matching methods that used a succession and combination of criteria including platform names, classes, countries, call-signs, IMO numbers. A total of 470 platform (mainly ship) instances were mapped to their unique ICES platform identifier from C17 (around 50% of the platform instances held in WOD) with 100% certainty. These mappings were used by Beacon to match incoming WMO platform IDs to a C17 URN and, using the mapping held in the NVS between C17 and L06, to the L06 category. These mappings have also been added to the Knowledge Base of the BODC Semantic Analyser as blank node RDF triples so that they are available for re-use.

6.1.4.4. Instruments

In Beacon, “instrument” is variable-specific and it represents a key element of the method used to create a measurement. The common vocabulary selected for the harmonisation of instruments (whether a sensor or a sampling device) is the NVS L05 SeaDataNet device categories vocabulary (<http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05/>) which captures instrument types rather than instrument models. Whenever possible, instrument models were also matched to their unique identifier from the NVS L22 SeaVoX Device Catalogue. However this information was not often available or it was not always easy to link it to a given variable. A review of how data models capture those elements of methodology will be needed in the future to ensure that a parameter can be easily connected to the method used to derive it, and that this information is readily usable by software.

- **CMEMS:** the instrument field for each parameter was populated from a mapping between CMEMS WMO_INST_TYPE and L05 or L22, hardcoded in Beacon. Failing this, Beacon uses

¹ https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/world-ocean-database/CODES/s_3_platform.html

the CMEMS Data Type Bigram which was manually mapped to L05, to fill the gaps. It was not always possible to populate this field and, in the future, effort will be needed to better harmonise this information across the BDIs.

- **EMODnet Chemistry:** the variable-specific L22 code is obtained from the metadata header of the SeaDataNet data file, information which is kept in the EMODnet Chemistry data product. If this field is empty, then Beacon uses the L05 code held in the CDI metadata record. However this field can contain multiple L05 identifiers if the data come from devices belonging to more than one device category. A review of the relationships between instruments and variables at the CDI discovery levels and/or more consistent use of the L22 field in the data file header would help resolve this issue and improve recording or provenance and traceability.
- **WOD:** instrument type and model information was extracted from WOD code table v_5_instrument² which also contains information about platforms, and mapped to an exact L22 concept or the closest broader L22 or L05 concepts. These mappings are currently hardcoded in Beacon but will be made available via the BODC Semantic Analyser.

6.2. CW Duplicates Tool - CWdt

6.2.1. Overview

Because the EWB harvests data from overlapping global and regional infrastructures (such as CMEMS, EMODnet, and WOD), the raw extracted subsets frequently contain duplicate station observations. The **CW Duplicates Tool** is tasked with identifying and flagging these spatial and temporal duplicates.

Developed by the POKaPOK team (<https://pokapok.org>) the tool evaluates potential duplicates based on mandatory metadata profiles (e.g., exact coordinate proximity, overlapping timestamps, and instrument types) alongside user-defined tolerance criteria.

The tool executes a multi-step analytical process:

1. **Detection and statistics:** Scans the harmonized input datasets to build a statistical matrix of potential duplicates.
2. **Decision tree evaluation:** Applies a programmatic decision tree (figure 5) to assess which duplicate record possesses the higher quality flags, richer metadata, or better vertical resolution.

² https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/world-ocean-database/CODES/v_5_instrument.html

Figure 4 – decision tree.

3. **Output generation:** Produces two primary downstream files in comma-separated values (CSV) format:
 - a. *The Duplicates List:* A comprehensive log mapping all paired redundant records for quality control transparency.
 - b. *The Discard List:* A precise exclusion list specifying which exact rows or profiles must be filtered out to generate a clean, unique dataset product.

Deployment and access: The CW Duplicates Tool is deployed as an executable method on the [D4Science Cloud Computing Platform](#) under the "**Duplicates-tools**" method tab. The complete source code is open-source and archived on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20605786>), with a comprehensive operating guide located within the workbench workspace at [Eutrophication-workbench/0-Documentation](#).

Find the resource in the blue-cloud catalogue under the Eutrophication workbench Vlab: https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Eutrophication-Workbench/cw_duplicates_tool.

6.3. FileForge - FF

6.3.1. Overview and core architecture

FileForge is a data transformation engine developed by [lfremer](#) that bridges the gap between raw cloud-optimized analytical data and standard desktop oceanographic software formats. It acts as the workflow’s compilation layer, consuming the high-volume Parquet datasets produced by Beacon and refining them based on the quality control actions dictated by the CW Duplicates Tool.

Figure 5 – FileForge overview

Architecturally, the tool executes its pipeline across three distinct modules:

1. **Input ingestion and flattening layer:** Reads multidimensional spatial data models and flattens them into tabular in-memory objects (such as Pandas or Polars DataFrames). If external descriptive metadata arrays are supplied, they are systematically mapped and appended to their corresponding observation rows.
2. **Processing application layer:** Applies user-defined transformation algorithms, QC routines, and filtering matrices to the active dataset using customized configuration arguments.
3. **Format-specific writing layer:** Constructs the final file structure. Because different data specifications handle file headers and global variables differently, this module customizes metadata indexing to exploit the strengths of each format type while strictly preserving structural data integrity.

6.3.2. Supported interoperable output formats

Based on a user-defined configuration execution template, FileForge can reorganize and compile active datasets into three primary computational formats, maximizing downstream system interoperability:

- **Apache Parquet (tabular formats):** High-performance, columnar storage layouts optimized for distributed, cloud-native big data analytics.
- **ODV Spreadsheet collections (tabular station data):** Formatted and column-indexed specifically for native desktop consumption or cloud deployment within the Ocean Data View (ODV) and webODV ecosystems.
- **NetCDF files (gridded and profile formats):** Self-describing, Climate and Forecast (CF) metadata-compliant array files tailored for climate modeling, data assimilation, and spatial Geographic Information Systems (GIS).

6.3.3. Upstream pipeline integration and FAIR provenance

Within the EWB workflow, FileForge functions as the terminal consolidation engine. It directly consumes high-volume, Apache Parquet datasets harvested by the Beacon data lake engine and refines them using the analytical outputs of the CW duplicates Tool.

During this compilation phase, FileForge dynamically parses the `Duplicate List` and `Discarded List` produced during the deduplication phase. The engine filters out duplicate profiles while embedding full tracking flags that trace records back to their original institutional source infrastructures. Simultaneously, FileForge automatically populates processing logs to document exact software versions, runtime parameters, and processing methods. This comprehensive lineage tracking ensures strict compliance with **FAIR data provenance principles**, making the generation of any data product completely transparent and reproducible.

6.3.4. Running FileForge (FF) on the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP)

FileForge is exposed as an executable cloud service on the **D4Science Cloud Computing Platform (CCP)** under the "**Converting Tool**" method group.

6.3.4.1. Resource allocations and profile selection

When launching the tool, users can select between two distinct server profiles* depending on data volumes and current cluster queue states:

- **16 GB RAM Profile:** The standard processing node configuration. This instance operates efficiently for regional workflows (for example, compiling the Mediterranean Sea EOVS collections spanning 1950–2025). Because D4Science maintains a high volume of 16 GB nodes, scheduling queues for this instance are typically short or non-existent.
- **32 GB RAM Profile:** Hosted on advanced, hardware-accelerated GPU cluster nodes. This profile provides superior operational speeds and expanded memory capacity for **global collections**. However, because these nodes are shared across intensive Virtual Research Environments (VREs), users may encounter brief scheduling queues if concurrency is high.

Figure 6 – FileForge as CCP method under “Converting Tool” tab.

* The configuration fields and operating procedures are identical across both the 16 GB and 32 GB profiles.

6.3.4.2. Technical parameter reference guide

To execute a FF conversion routine, open the method interface by clicking the green execution icon on the CCP tab (Figure 7). the method configuration will appear on the right hand side of the window as shown in Figure 8. The step by step guide to configure the execution method and parameter fields needed are explained in Table 4 below.

Figure 7 – FileForge method execution.

Parameter Field	Operational Requirement & Expected Format
Configuration file	The absolute URL or VRE workspace path pointing to the execution template. Users can pass an individual YAML configuration file, or point directly to a parent workspace directory to execute all nested configuration templates sequentially.

	<div data-bbox="548 296 1365 604"> <p>Access your workspace ✕</p> <p>Select an item or drag and drop it to a proper input</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2_CWduplicatesTool 3_FileForge <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Configuration_files <ul style="list-style-type: none"> wb2_netcdf_config_2.yaml wb2_netcdf_config_2_chunked.yaml wb2_netcdf config 2 clean.yaml <p style="text-align: right;">SELECT</p> </div> <p style="text-align: center; margin: 10px 0;">or</p> <div data-bbox="548 705 1365 1014"> <p>Access your workspace ✕</p> <p>Select an item or drag and drop it to a proper input</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> wb2_netcdf_config_2_clean.yaml wb2_odv_config_2.yaml wb2_odv_config_2_chunked.yaml wb2_odv_config_2_clean.yaml wb2_odv_config_timeseries.yaml wb2_parquet config 2.yaml <p style="text-align: right;">SELECT</p> </div>
<p>Data folder</p>	<p>The target directory containing the input data. Following the system pipeline, this field must point to the parent folder containing the unrefined Parquet files extracted via the Beacon data lake engine.</p> <div data-bbox="548 1188 1365 1497"> <p>Access your workspace ✕</p> <p>Select an item or drag and drop it to a proper input</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1_DataLakeQuery <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Merged_notebooks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> output <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EUTRO_CMEMS EUTRO_EC EUTRO_WOD <p style="text-align: right;">SELECT</p> <p style="font-size: small; margin-top: 5px;">* Logging Level</p> </div>
<p>External folder</p>	<p>This field defines auxiliary datasets required by the processing scripts. To ensure correct pipeline execution, users can map up to six inputs here. In standard workflows, you must insert the directory path containing the CW Duplicates Tool output files (specifically the Duplicate List, Discard List, and the associated processing log file needed to verify the software version footprint).</p>

<p>Destination folder (optional)</p>	<p>Specifies the cloud storage destination for the generated output products. If left blank, the tool defaults to saving final data objects into the root directory of your personal user Workbench folder.</p>
<p>Annotation (optional)</p>	<p>A customizable string to override the default timestamp folder nomenclature (YYYYMMDDhhmmss_fileforge). For example, defining the annotation string as med_chlorophyll_final forces FileForge to name the output directory med_chlorophyll_final_fileforge. This protects historical datasets from being overwritten and simplifies multi-version comparison tracking.</p>

<p>Method execution</p>	<p>After having configured the above, the method can be executed.</p>
	<p>When the method is successful, the results will be shown in the destination folder.</p>

Table 4 – FF method execution step by step guide

6.3.4.3. Output management and compression protocols

Upon a successful execution run, the logs and finalized data objects are deployed to the assigned destination directory.

When generating webODV Spreadsheet Collections, FileForge automatically bundles the plain-text spreadsheet assets inside compressed .zip archives. Because raw oceanographic ODV text matrixes can expand exponentially, this compression routine drastically simplifies web visualization loading times and file transfers (for instance, compressing an unzipped 80 GB text collection down to an optimized 5 GB archive package).

6.3.5. System registries, code access, and documentation

FileForge is deployed as a cloud service method on the [D4Science Cloud Computing Platform](#). The underlying source code is maintained on Ifremer's GitLab instance available on <https://zenodo.org/records/20596096>.

Find the resource in the blue-cloud catalogue under the Eutrophication workbench Vlab: https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Eutrophication-Workbench/fileforge_in_eutrophication_workbench_ccp

Comprehensive Operator Technical Manual <https://data.d4science.net/5B1Tt>

6.4. webODV

The final component of the workbench architecture is **webODV**, a web-based implementation of the gold-standard **Ocean Data View (ODV)** software. It serves as the interactive visualization, exploration, and delivery layer of the Eutrophication Workbench ecosystem.

Rather than forcing users to download massive raw files locally to visually inspect their data, webODV hosts the finalized, deduplicated, and FileForge-processed data collections directly in the cloud. It provides an intuitive, browser-based user interface that replicates the core capabilities of the desktop ODV application.

Through webODV, users can:

- **Interactive Visualization:** Instantly generate high-quality station maps, vertical section plots, scatter plots (such as Temperature vs. Salinity or Chlorophyll-a vs. Nutrients), and temporal surface animations.
- **Quality Control Inspection:** Interactively examine individual station profiles, visually identify outliers, and check data distribution across distinct bathymetric depths or marine regions.
- **Custom Subsetting & Extraction:** Apply fine-tuned visual filters directly on the canvas to isolate specific data points, and subsequently export these tailored subsets into regional data packages for localized research.

By integrating webODV as the terminal node of the architecture, the workbench ensures that the final data products are immediately actionable, enabling swift scientific discovery and assessment of marine eutrophication trends without local software dependencies.

Deployment & Access: [webODV](#) has been deployed as a web application in jupyterhub. The software is developed and maintained by Dr. Sebastian Mieruch and Prof. Dr. Reiner Schlitzer at the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI), and its specialized manuals can be referenced at:

- Getting started with webODV: <https://explore.webodv.awi.de/docs/odv-online-getting-started.pdf>
- webODV How-to guide: <https://explore.webodv.awi.de/docs/odv-online-howto.pdf>
- ODV Full documentation: <https://odv.awi.de/documentation>
- ODV blue cloud deployment documentation: after starting the webapp go to the tab Docs.

7. Eutrophication workbench workflows

Operational workflows within the EWB VLab are split into two primary tracks tailored to the user's objective. For example, if the user wants to reproduce the EWB H&S EOVS data collection output or adapt the workflow to its own needs. The two groups as described in [section 5.2.1](#) are: the **Standard End-User Workflow** (a guided, step-by-step hybrid pipeline) and the **Developer/Advanced User Workflow** (for component customization and direct API and method manipulation).

7.1. EWB VLab directory reference map

To maintain structural clarity, the following layout details the role of each directory within the [EWB VLab workspace](#) ecosystem:

```
VRE Folders/Eutrophication-Workbench/
├── 0_Documentation/ # System and user guides, and tool technical manuals
├── 1_BEACON/ # Core BEACON data-querying notebooks examples.
├── 2_CWduplicates-tool/ # Deduplication YAML configurations, metadata rules, and Logs
├── 3_FileForge/ # Format transmutation layouts and YAML configuration files
├── 4_webODV/ # Synced ODV data spreadsheets and binary collections
├── REPO/ # EWB repository, old test
├── user_workflow/ # Contains the master notebook for the user workflow initialization.
└── README.md # Root environment overview file
```

The [README.md](#) describes the standard EWB workflow and provides descriptions of expected inputs and outputs on each step.

7.1.1. Master notebook

Due to the lack of an orchestration layer, the master notebook in `workspace/VREFolders/Eutrophication-Workbench/user_workflow/0_Start_Here_RUNME.ipynb` and published in the blue cloud catalogue (Reyes Suarez, 2026b) aims to set up the complete folder structure and configuration files needed to run the workflow.

1. Open [JupyterLab](#) in the EWB VLab.
2. Navigate to your home workspace:
`/home/jovyan/workspace/VREFolders/Eutrophication-Workbench/user_workflow/`
3. Create a **copy** of the folder:
`../user_workflow/0_Start_Here_RUNME.ipynb` in your `/home/jovyan/workspace/`
4. Open and run the notebook in your copied folder.
5. When prompted, enter:
 - Your initials (user identifier)
 - Start year and month (YYYYMM format)
 - End year and month (YYYYMM format)
 - Depth range from (metres)
 - Depth range to (metres)

once run, the user will find the following directory tree created:

```
[root]/
├── 1_DatalakeQuery/
│   ├── Merged_notebooks/
│   │   ├── 01_EWB_BEACON=merged-v1.5.4_FILTER=BDI-FeatureType_VAR=allEOV_OUT=parquet.ipynb
│   │   └── output/
│   └──
├── 2_CWduplicates-tool/
│   ├── cache_empty/
│   ├── Configuration_files/
│   │   ├── Config_Profiles/
│   │   └── cw_user_config.yaml
│   └── outputs/
└── 3_FileForge/
    ├── Configuration_files/
    │   └── [All files copied from the source FileForge config folder]
    └── output/
```

7.2. Core operational principles

Regardless of the workflow track, the entire infrastructure operates under strict scientific constraints to guarantee transparency, reproducibility, and rigorous data provenance:

- **Hybrid execution framework:** The EWB workflow is intrinsically hybrid; it is not fully automated and intentionally relies on user checkpoint decisions and manual interventions to maintain scientific control.
- **Isolated environments:** Each analytical step runs inside its own dedicated execution environment (JupyterLab, CCP, or webODV), preventing environment pollution and cross-tool dependency conflicts.
- **Core EOVS Coverage:** The workflows are optimized to ingest, clean, and export data for the EOVS described in [section 3](#).

The functional steps across both workflows depend on the four core system components ([section 6](#)) integrated into the EWB VLab. Keep in mind (as stated in [section 5](#)) that to interact with the data collections, analytical notebooks, and processing engines, users must first access the EWB VLab environment upon registration on the D4Science e-infrastructure:

Component	Purpose	Where to Access
Beacon	Data access, subsetting, merging, harmonization	JupyterLab tab using beacon endpoints
CWdt	Detect and classify duplicates	Inside the CCP tab
FF	Remove annotated duplicates, convert to ODV	Inside the CCP tab
webODV	Explore and extract ready-to-use datasets	WebODV tab

Table 5 - Integrated tools matrix

7.2.1. “Standard” End-User workflow execution

The end-user workflow leverages **pre-packaged scripts** and **configuration templates** to systematically guide researchers from raw BDI to an analysis-ready oceanographic collection ([Figure 3](#)). These steps are summarized in the [EWB welcome page](#) as well.

As described above if the objective is to reproduce or adapt the EWB workflow the user must follow the steps below and detailed in figure 9.

[Step 0: Setup] → [Step 1: BEACON Query] → [Step 2: CW Duplicates] → [Step 3: FileForge] → [Step 4: webODV]

Figure 8 – Detailed end-user workflow schema.

7.2.1.1. Step 0 - Master notebook

1. Launch JupyterLab from the top menu of the EWB VLab dashboard.
2. Locate the master template folder:
 /home/jovyan/workspace/VREFolders/Eutrophication-Workbench/user_workflow/
3. Copy the setup notebook 0_Start_Here_RUNME.ipynb directly into your root home workspace directory (/home/jovyan/workspace).
4. Open and execute the notebook. The interactive script will prompt for the following operational inputs:
 - a. User initials (for tracking provenance)
 - b. Temporal boundary constraints (Format: YYYYMM start and end dates)
 - c. Vertical boundary depth constraints (Minimum and maximum depth values in meters)

⚠ The default time and depth range are **2010-01-01T00:00:00-2010-01-31T23:59:59** and **0-10m** for the **global ocean**, bear in mind that this is also the default values in the jupyter notebook `01_EWB_BEACON=merged-v1.5.4_FILTER=BDI-FeatureType_VAR=allEOV_OUT=parquet.ipynb` in step 1, thus **if you change the default values you will need to change you notebook as well.**

⚠ Step 0 must be executed completely before running any other step in the pipeline. It automatically provisions the standardized directory tree structure ([section 7.1.1](#)) necessary to run the workflow.

7.2.1.2. Step 1 - Beacon query

1. Within JupyterLab, navigate into the freshly provisioned path:
`1_DataLakeQuery/Merged_notebooks/`
2. Open and run the primary extraction notebook: `01_EWB_BEACON=merged-v1.5.4_FILTER=BDI-FeatureType_VAR=allEOV_OUT=parquet.ipynb`
3. Provide your active Blue-Cloud authorization token when prompted by the script.

Output: A unified, harmonized dataset compiled in Apache Parquet format, filtered by BDI and feature type, deposited in `1_DataLakeQuery/outputs/`.

⚠ Authentication Note: Tokens must be retrieved via the top panel: *How-to* → *Authorization-How-to* as described in [section 5.2.2](#). Tokens expire after 24 hours. If an error occurs during execution, generate a new token, apply it to the environment, and restart the JupyterLab server.

7.2.1.3. Step 2 - CWdt

1. Access the CCP tab from the main VLab dashboard.
2. Select and launch the CWdt execution method (detailed in [section 6.2](#)).
3. Populate the required parameter fields:
 - i. Direct the tool's input parameter to the Parquet data files generated in [Step 1](#).
 - ii. Mount the configuration file (`cw_user_config.yaml`) created during [Step 0](#) and the rest of information needed.
4. Execute the CCP method.

Output: A structured output located at `2_CWduplicates-tool/outputs/` containing explicit, indexed Duplicate List, Discard List and logs in .csv format.

7.2.1.4. Step 3 - FF

1. From the CCP dashboard, launch the FileForge method instance.
2. Populate the required parameter fields (detailed in [section 6.3.4](#))
 - i. Point to the raw outputs from Step 2.

- ii. Select the appropriate operational template file located in `3_FileForge/Configuration_files/` (e.g., `Wb2__config.yaml`).
3. Execute the method to clean or flag overlapping profiles based on the selected criteria.

Output: The final compiled files are pushed back to the user workspace environment under a dedicated execution path, such as:

`3_FileForge/outputs/output/wb2_merged.txt`.

7.2.1.5. Step 4 - webODV

1. Copy the final .txt dataset generated by FileForge in Step 3 into the dedicated webODV synchronization folder: `/home/jovyan/4_webODV/`
2. Open the webODV tab from the EWB interface
3. Initialize an import routine to convert the text spreadsheet matrices into an active, compressed .odv collection.

Output: A fully validated, interactive .odv data collection ready for research dissemination or localized export.

[Video tutorial of the full EWB end user workflow](#) can be found at the following path in the EWB workspace: `/workspace/VREFolders/Eutrophication-Workbench/0_Documentation/EBW_demo.mp4`

8. Recommendations for BDIs

During the development and cross-infrastructure integration phases of the EWB workflow, several systematic data disharmonies, metadata gaps, and structural inconsistencies were identified across the contributing BDIs.

To realize true machine-to-machine (M2M) interoperability and support automated cloud harvesting engines like beacon, the EWB framework establishes a formalized data feedback loop. This section details concrete, actionable recommendations directed at the primary data providers to improve the semantic and structural quality of upstream marine data products.

8.1. Cross-BDI Structural Recommendations

8.1.1. Publication and governance of machine-readable vocabularies

To facilitate smooth semantic mapping layers—both manual and automated machine-to-machine integrations—all BDIs must publish their internal code lists, platform designations, and data

categorization schemas using open, web-accessible controlled vocabulary servers (e.g., NERC Vocabulary Server, SeaDataNet Vocabularies).

The Challenge: Systems frequently rely on hardcoded text strings or obscure, closed internal code tables (such as Copernicus Marine Service data type Bigrams or World Ocean Database internal code lists).

The Recommendation: Migrate all proprietary code tables into standardized, machine-resolvable URI formats. This allows semantic mediation layers to translate incoming records on the fly without breaking pipeline parsing scripts.

8.1.2. Enrichment of 3 essential metadata : Cruise identifier, Platform and Instrument codes

Only well-described data can be properly reused by users. In the EWB Vlab use case, which relies in part on data collected during oceanographic cruises, the identification of duplicate records is effective only if three additional key metadata elements, besides date and position, are provided: the cruise identifier, the platform code, and the measuring instrument code.

The Challenge: Depending on the BDI, one of the 2 following metadata is typically used in preference : the cruise identifier or the platform code. Regarding the instrument code, it is either optional in at least one BDI or does not provide sufficient granularity.

The Recommendation: Extend the metadata schema to include both the cruise identifier and the platform codes, where applicable. Data providers should be encouraged not only to supply instrument codes, but also to do so at the finest level of granularity, i.e. at the level of individual parameters.

8.1.3. Implementation of globally unique granular identifiers

Duplicate matching algorithms require immutable anchors to track data provenance across distributed environments.

Feedbacks to BDIs and to data originators, following data processing through a workflow or a value chain, can be delivered efficiently provided that unique identifiers exist to precisely specify where and to what the feedback applies.

The Challenge: Data aggregates often lose granularity, assigning identifiers at the parent file level rather than tracking individual physical samples.

The Recommendation: Implement and enforce a globally unique identifier per profile, per time series, and per trajectory. These granular IDs must persist through all data extraction, aggregation, and reprocessing lifecycles.

8.2. BDI-Specific Targeted Recommendations

8.2.1. EMODnet Chemistry: Adopting standard feature types

To align fully with modern data lake discovery paradigms, EMODnet Chemistry must natively implement and expose explicit structural classification metadata within its core delivery models.

Action Item: Formally integrate the standard Climate and Forecast (CF) Conventions for FeatureTypes into the primary data schemas.

Reference Specification: Geometries must be strictly validated against the official NERC Vocabulary Server collection N03: CF Convention Feature Types ([NVS Collection N03](#)).

By explicitly tagging collections as `profile`, `timeSeries`, or `trajectory`, downstream tools can route datasets to appropriate analytical modules without inspecting every coordinate array.

8.2.2. Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS): Disentangling feature geometries and QC protocols

Data audits via the beacon engine revealed a series of geometry misalignments and unresolvable vertical references within CMEMS Biogeochemical (BGC) products.

Geometry Misalignments: Under the `feature_type` property, hybrid values (such as `trajectoryProfile` or `timeSeriesProfile`) are sometimes grouped inappropriately with legacy platform identification bigrams. For example the query below shows all the BIGRAMS associated when querying only `'trajectoryProfile'`, `'timeSeriesProfile'`:

```
# Observed structural disharmony in CMEMS active metadata arrays:
Unique_values_for_FEATURE_TYPE = ['trajectoryProfile', 'timeSeriesProfile']
Unique_values_for_BIGRAM       = ['GL', 'XB', 'BO', 'CT', 'SM', 'XX', 'ML', 'PF', 'MO']
```

Vertical Reference Anomalies (Missing Depth Fields): The pipeline flagged instances of observation data completely lacking explicit vertical coordinate (depth) references. While these values are labeled with a Quality Control flag of QC=9 (missing value), providing data records completely decoupled from their physical vertical context limits data utility. CMEMS should establish an automated validation feedback loop back to the originating data networks to guarantee that no physical profiles are published without localized spatial boundaries.

8.2.3. World Ocean Database (WOD): Harmonizing documentation and controlled terms

The World Ocean Database contains significant data volumes, but suffers from text string discrepancies within its metadata headers that complicate automated semantic parsing.

The Challenge: The text labels populated within the internal dataset metadata attribute frequently contradict the definitions and terms officially published in the WOD User Guide, companion web portals, and formal reference publications.

The Recommendation: Standardize the dataset text fields at the source level using invariant, restricted vocabulary lists to eliminate naming variation errors.

8.3. WOD Controlled Vocabulary Standardization Matrix

The table below outlines real-world structural discrepancies identified within the WOD data streams during EWB workflow integration, alongside the proposed controlled vocabularies needed to secure seamless machine interoperability:

Attribute Context	Observed text variance in data files	Reference source / discrepancy link	Proposed Controlled Vocabulary Constraint
Dataset Code	OSD, CTD, XBT, MBT	Inconsistent abbreviations vs. expanded terminology in documentation text.	Map strictly to standard instrumentation definitions (e.g., SeaDataNet L05 platform categories).
Originating Institution	Varied alphanumeric strings (e.g., NODC-USA, NCEI, US-NODC)	NCEI WOD Select Definitions	Enforce standardized EDMO (European Directory of Marine Organisations) codes or global SeaDataNet institution registers.
Platform / Ship Identification	Mixed numerical indexes and unvalidated free-text strings.	Discrepancies between official WOD cruise publications and embedded file headers.	Restrict entry inputs to standardized ICES platform codes or WMO numbers.

Table 6 – WOD Vocabulary standardization matrix

“Dataset” label in downloaded file (and held in Beacon’s monolith)	Comments	Recommendation
“CTD”	Matches CTD in the official WOD codelist	adopt existing or create controlled vocab URIs

“glider”	Matches GLD in the official WOD codelist	adopt existing or create controlled vocab URIs
“drifting buoy”	Matches DB in the official WOD codelist	adopt existing L06 or create controlled vocab URIs
“profiling float”	Matches PFL in the official WOD codelist	adopt existing or create controlled vocab URIs
“STD”	Not in the official WOD codelist. According to the WOD23 User manual, the “STD” “probe type” can be in a “OSD” dataset if they are low resolution or in a “CTD” dataset if they are high resolution.	adopt existing or create controlled vocab URIs
“bottle/rosette/net”	Not in the official WOD codelist. The closest would be Ocean Station Data (“OSD”) i.e. low resolution profile data from a range of collection and instrument types	
“towed CTD”	Matches UOR in the official WOD codelist	
“moored buoy”	Matches MRB in the official WOD codelist	

Table 7 – Examples of text found in WOD that would need to be constrained using controlled vocabularies to facilitate interoperability.

8.4. Conclusion: Closing the Feedback Loop

Building an interoperable marine data space is an iterative process. By establishing this programmatic feedback framework, the Eutrophication Workbench provides data providers with empirical evidence of data anomalies directly encountered during high-density workflows. BDIs are strongly encouraged to adopt these structural recommendations to move away from legacy, ad-hoc data structures and move toward fully automated, cloud-native FAIR data streams.

9. References

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10. Appendix

10.1. Global harmonized and standardized EOv dataset

Statistics from the above mentioned dataset before deduplication. The files is available at https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/Eutrophication-Workbench/blue-cloud2026_global_aggregated_and_harmonized_eutrophication_dataset

1. Global beacon query of all parameter EOvs per volume.

```
TIME_START = "1921-01-01T00:00:00"  
TIME_END = "2024-12-31T23:59:59"  
DEPTH_MIN = 0  
DEPTH_MAX = 10000  
LAT_MIN = -90  
LAT_MAX = 90  
LON_MIN = -180  
LON_MAX = 180
```

```
query = merged_client.query() # Create a new query builder instance  
query.add_select_column("COMMON_TIME", alias="TIME")  
query.add_select_column("COMMON_LATITUDE", alias="LATITUDE")  
query.add_select_column("COMMON_LONGITUDE", alias="LONGITUDE")  
  
#DEPTH  
query.add_select_column("COMMON_DEPTH", alias="DEPTH")  
query.add_select_column("COMMON_DEPTH_QC", alias="DEPTH_QC")  
query.add_select_column("COMMON_DEPTH_UNITS", alias="DEPTH_UNITS")  
query.add_select_column("COMMON_DEPTH_P01", alias="DEPTH_P01")  
query.add_select_column("COMMON_DEPTH_P06", alias="DEPTH_P06")  
  
# CHLOROPHYLL  
query.add_select_column(f"COMMON_{chl_col}", alias= chl_col)  
query.add_select_column(f"COMMON_{chl_col}_QC", alias=chl_col + "_QC")
```

```

query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_{chl_col}_UNITS", alias=chl_col + "_UNITS")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_{chl_col}_P01", alias=chl_col + "_P01")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_{chl_col}_P06", alias=chl_col + "_P06")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_CHLOROPHYLL_L05", alias="CHLOROPHYLL_L05")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_CHLOROPHYLL_L22", alias="CHLOROPHYLL_L22")

#OXYGEN PER VOLUME
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_OXYGEN_{unit}", alias=oxy_col)
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_OXYGEN_{unit}_QC", alias=oxy_col + "_QC")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_OXYGEN_{unit}_UNITS", alias=oxy_col + "_UNITS")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_OXYGEN_{unit}_P01", alias=oxy_col + "_P01")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_OXYGEN_{unit}_P06", alias=oxy_col + "_P06")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_OXYGEN_L05", alias="OXYGEN_L05")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_OXYGEN_L22", alias="OXYGEN_L22")

# NITRATE PER VOLUME
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_NITRATE_{unit}", alias=nit_col)
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_NITRATE_{unit}_QC", alias=nit_col + "_QC")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_NITRATE_{unit}_UNITS", alias=nit_col + "_UNITS")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_NITRATE_{unit}_P01", alias=nit_col + "_P01")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_NITRATE_{unit}_P06", alias=nit_col + "_P06")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_NITRATE_L05", alias="NITRATE_L05")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_NITRATE_L22", alias="NITRATE_L22")

# NITRATE PLUS NITRITE PER VOLUME
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_NITRATE_NITRITE_{unit}", alias=nit_nit_col)
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_NITRATE_NITRITE_{unit}_QC", alias=nit_nit_col + "_QC")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_NITRATE_NITRITE_{unit}_UNITS", alias=nit_nit_col +
"_UNITS")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_NITRATE_NITRITE_{unit}_P01", alias=nit_nit_col + "_P01")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_NITRATE_NITRITE_{unit}_P06", alias=nit_nit_col + "_P06")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_NITRATE_NITRITE_L05", alias="NITRATE_NITRITE_L05")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_NITRATE_NITRITE_L22", alias="NITRATE_NITRITE_L22")

# AMMONIUM PER VOLUME
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_AMMONIUM_{unit}", alias=amm_col)
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_AMMONIUM_{unit}_QC", alias=amm_col + "_QC")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_AMMONIUM_{unit}_UNITS", alias=amm_col + "_UNITS")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_AMMONIUM_{unit}_P01", alias=amm_col + "_P01")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_AMMONIUM_{unit}_P06", alias=amm_col + "_P06")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_AMMONIUM_L05", alias="AMMONIUM_L05")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_AMMONIUM_L22", alias="AMMONIUM_L22")

# PHOSPHATE PER VOLUME
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_PHOSPHATE_{unit}", alias=pho_col)
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_PHOSPHATE_{unit}_QC", alias=pho_col + "_QC")

```

```

query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_PHOSPHATE_{unit}_UNITS", alias=pho_col + "_UNITS")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_PHOSPHATE_{unit}_P01", alias=pho_col + "_P01")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_PHOSPHATE_{unit}_P06", alias=pho_col + "_P06")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_PHOSPHATE_L05", alias="PHOSPHATE_L05")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_PHOSPHATE_L22", alias="PHOSPHATE_L22")

# SILICATE PER VOLUME
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_SILICATE_{unit}", alias= sil_col)
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_SILICATE_{unit}_QC", alias=sil_col + "_QC")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_SILICATE_{unit}_UNITS", alias=sil_col + "_UNITS")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_SILICATE_{unit}_P01", alias=sil_col + "_P01")
query.add_select_column(F"COMMON_SILICATE_{unit}_P06", alias=sil_col + "_P06")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_SILICATE_L05", alias="SILICATE_L05")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_SILICATE_L22", alias="SILICATE_L22")

# SALINITY
query.add_select_column("COMMON_SALINITY", alias="SALINITY")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_SALINITY_QC", alias="SALINITY_QC")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_SALINITY_UNITS", alias="SALINITY_UNITS")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_SALINITY_P01", alias="SALINITY_P01")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_SALINITY_P06", alias="SALINITY_P06")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_SALINITY_L05", alias="SALINITY_L05")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_SALINITY_L22", alias="SALINITY_L22")

# TEMPERATURE
query.add_select_column("COMMON_TEMPERATURE", alias="TEMPERATURE")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_TEMPERATURE_QC", alias="TEMPERATURE_QC")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_TEMPERATURE_UNITS", alias="TEMPERATURE_UNITS")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_TEMPERATURE_P01", alias="TEMPERATURE_P01")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_TEMPERATURE_P06", alias="TEMPERATURE_P06")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_TEMPERATURE_L05", alias="TEMPERATURE_L05")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_TEMPERATURE_L22", alias="TEMPERATURE_L22")

# add metadata columns
query.add_select_column("COMMON_PLATFORM_L06", alias="PLATFORM_L06")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_PLATFORM_C17", alias="PLATFORM_C17")
query.add_select_column("SOURCE_BDI")
query.add_select_column("SOURCE_BDI_DATASET_ID")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_EDMO_CODE", alias="EDMO_CODE")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_CSR", alias="CSR")

query.add_select_column("COMMON_HARMONIZATION_DATE")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_BDI_SNAPSHOT_DATE")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_BDI_MONOLITH_VERSION")

#metadata from monoliths
query.add_select_column("bigram", alias="BIGRAM")
    
```

```

query.add_select_column("dataset", alias="WOD_DATASET")
query.add_select_column("COMMON_FEATURE_TYPE", alias="FEATURE_TYPE")
# important to generate the odv format
query.add_select_column("COMMON_ODV_TAG", alias="ODV_TAG")

# Apply filters to the query. WE KEEP ONLY SAMPLES WITH ASSOCIATED TEMPERATURE AND SALINITY
# MEASUREMENTS
query.add_filter(
    OrFilter([IsNotNullFilter(chl_col),
              IsNotNullFilter(oxy_col),
              IsNotNullFilter(nit_col),
              IsNotNullFilter(nit_nit_col),
              IsNotNullFilter(amm_col),
              IsNotNullFilter(pho_col),
              IsNotNullFilter(sil_col),
              ])
)

query.add_range_filter("TIME", TIME_START, TIME_END) # You can adjust the date range as
# needed. The format is ISO 8601.

query.add_range_filter("DEPTH", DEPTH_MIN, DEPTH_MAX) # Depth range

query.add_range_filter("LATITUDE", LAT_MIN, LAT_MAX) # Latitude range from -90 to 90 for
# full range (you can adjust as needed)
query.add_range_filter("LONGITUDE", LON_MIN, LON_MAX) # Longitude range from -180 to 180 for
# full range (you can adjust as needed)

```

Exploring the global harmonized and standardized eutrophication data collection the following statistics were retrieved:

- Total number of BDI counts: 1316427551
- Data availability per BDI:
-

SOURCE_BDI	COUNT	PERCENTAGE, %
BEACON_WOD	637936353	48.5
BEACON_CMEMS_BGC	625694279	47.5

BEACON_EMODNET_CHEMISTRY	52796919	4.0
--------------------------	----------	-----

Table 8 – Data availability per BDI from the Global Harmonized and Standardized eutrophication data collection.

Figure 10 – Record counts and time availability of feature types from the Global Harmonized and Standardized eutrophication data collection.

Figure 11 – Record counts and time availability of WOD dataset type from the Global Harmonized and Standardized eutrophication data collection.

Figure 12 – Record counts and time availability of CMEMS bigrams from the Global Harmonized and Standardized eutrophication data collection.

Figure 13 – Record counts vs feature type on each BDI from the Global Harmonized and Standardized eutrophication data collection.

Figure 14 – Percentage of SeaDataNet Platform categories L06 per SOURCE_BDI from the Global Harmonized and Standardized EOV data collection.

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Ecosystem Workbench Users handbook

Work Package	WP3 Developing and testing analytical Blue Cloud workbenches for generating highly qualified data collections (Essential Ocean Variables, EOV)
Task	T3.4 EOV Workbench for ecosystems
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Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.2	26/06/2026	Schickele Alexandre (ETHZ)	Final version for submission

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
EBV	Essential Biodiveristy Variables
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information System
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
CCP	Cloud Computing Platform
CEPHALOPOD	Comprehensible Ensemble Pipeline for Habitat modelling of Large Ocean Plankton Observation Datasets

Keywords

EOSC; EOv; EBv; Workbenches; species distribution model; Plankton; Biodiversity; Observations

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Table 1 - Collection of observation-based, monthly-resolved environmental features at the global scale and available in this course material. Figure based on Schickele et al. (2025; supplementary data S1)

1. Introduction

The volume of accessible marine pelagic observations increases exponentially, now incorporating diverse data types such as metagenomics and quantitative imaging. In consequence, standardized and accessible modelling frameworks becomes critical to predict biogeographic patterns in space and time and across this wealth of marine observations. Within the Blue-Cloud 2026 EU-Horizon project, we introduce the [Ecosystem Workbench](#) whose primary objective is to improve the availability, quality, and interoperability of large collections of plankton observations and their associated extrapolated biogeographies, to diagnose Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs).

2. The CEPHALOPD modeling workflow

At the core of this workbench lies CEPHALOPOD, which stands for *Comprehensible Ensemble Pipeline for Habitat modelling of Large Ocean Plankton Observation Datasets* (Schickele et al. 2025). It is a collection of R scripts designed to handle complex, sparse, and biased marine organism observation data and turn them into continuous estimates of their spatial distribution. The pipeline uses cutting-edge data processing, statistical techniques, and machine learning methods — all wrapped in a highly automated workflow. CEPHALOPOD includes standardized steps for pre-processing, modelling, and quality control, making it easy to compare spatial distribution outputs generated from different types of observation data, such as presence-only records, continuous measurements (e.g., abundance or biomass), or proportional data (e.g., metagenomic reads). It is scalable for modelling many species at once, making it a powerful tool for marine biodiversity assessment. At the same time, its high degree of automation and explicit quality checks generate user-friendly PDF reports that guide non-experts to interpret model accuracy and reliability. Accessible biological data includes initiatives such as AtlantECO, OBIS, GBIF, Ocean Microbiomics, that also integrate biological outputs from platforms such as Ecotaxa and ELIXIR (MGNify) (Vogt et al., 2026; Paoli et al. 2022).

3. Description of the workbench features

3.1 The Virtual Research Environment (VRE)

To run the CEPHALOPOD workflow interactively, you can access it on the Bluecloud VRE by following the steps below. The VRE provides with 8 cores and 32 GB of memory, sufficient for a general usage across most case studies.

1. Register on the Bluecloud at: <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/home>
2. Register to the Ecosystem Workbench at: <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/ecosystem-workbench>
3. To open the VRE, go to the RStudio panel in the top menu bar and click on Start RStudio.
4. Locate the `~/blue-cloud-dataspace/Ecosystem_Workbench/All_materials` folder. Using the bottom right panel on RStudio, copy the `./CEPHALOPOD_training` folder in your `/home` and set the work directory at the root of the CEPHALOPOD folder, which should be `~/CEPHALOPOD_training`
5. Navigate to and open the file located at: `/code/00_config.R`
6. All necessary libraries should already be installed. If not, on the first use, execute the R library installation commands line by line, responding affirmatively to any interactive prompts. This ensures the installation of all necessary libraries and corresponding versions.

Please note: You should now be ready to use CEPHALOPOD within the VRE. Please read the complete handbook, including technical description of the CEPHALOPOD workflow and a practical in the sections below.

3.2 The Cloud Computing Platform (CCP)

For automated execution of the CEPHALOPOD workflow, we recommend using the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP). To access it, open the Analytics Engine from the top menu bar and select CCP. CEPHALOPOD is available in the left-hand panel under [Uncategorized/Hackathon CEPHALOPOD with parallelization](#).

The CCP implementation runs CEPHALOPOD through Docker containers and is designed for large-scale automated analyses. To facilitate automation, only a subset of the parameters described in the CEPHALOPOD Handbook is currently available, including the selection of biological datasets and environmental predictors. In return, the CCP provides substantially greater computational resources, making it particularly suitable for modelling large numbers of taxa simultaneously to derive biodiversity related EOVs and EBVs (e.g., phytoplankton diversity). Users will receive an email notification when a run has completed.

3.3 EOVs and EBVs visualization with Cephaloview

The EOVs and EBVs generated within the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, available through [here](#), can be explored interactively using the Cephaloview application. Cephaloview can be launched directly from the workbench top menu bar by selecting Cephaloview App.

The application provides access to a wide range of plankton products, including biodiversity EBVs derived from multiple observation types, species distribution maps, and biomass based EOVs. Users can browse, visualize, and compare these products through an intuitive web interface.

4. Description of the CEPHALOPOD file structure

Now that you have CEPHALOPOD at your designated installation path in the VRE, you should see several subfolders.

Here we provide an overview of their content and use.

- The `./master.R` script contains an example script demonstrating the utilization of CEPHALOPOD. This file serves as a template to be customized or replicated for each usage instance of CEPHALOPOD (e.g., by modifying the data source or model parameters; we will come to that later).
- The `./code` folder contains the collection of R scripts, each corresponding to the function associated with a distinct step within the CEPHALOPOD workflow. All R scripts are numbered in their order of use, matching the numbering in the `./master.R` script.
- The `./function` folder contains custom R functions of general use across the different steps (e.g., definition of colorbars, operations on spatial data).
- The `./data` folder corresponds to the directory containing input data and model cache.
- The `./output` designates the directory where CEPHALOPOD automatically stores its output for each instance or case study.

5. CEPHALOPOD technical documentation

Please note, this section is not a practical guide. The code chunks are here to illustrate the described function parameters and CEPHALOPOD options you have access to.

Step 0. Initialize the session

Now that you understand how to install CEPHALOPOD and what it contains, let's dive into an example from a master script. Please note that the following example does not correspond to a real case study and only aims to illustrate how to run CEPHALOPOD in a practical manner. For further information, please refer to associated publications and the technical documentation present in the R scripts in `./code`.

The `./master.R` script starts by a cleanup of your current R session and defines your CEPHALOPOD instance in the `run_name` object. The call to `./code/00_config.R` will load all necessary libraries and functions in your R environment.

```
{r}
rm(list=ls())
closeAllConnections()
setwd("/your_installation_path")
source(file = "./code/00_config.R")
run_name <- "test"
```

Step 1. List available biological data

We kickstart the modeling process by identifying the species available for analysis, from a defined source (**Figure 1** – step 1). We select these species based on specific criteria, such as a minimum sample size, the depth range for sampling, and the temporal range of the data. This selection ensures that the subsequent modeling efforts focus on species that meet the desired criteria. Parameters are the following :

- **DATA_SOURCE**: either "occurrence", "biomass", "abundance", "MAG", "custom". This parameter will redirect the query to the appropriate database to source the data from. The latter corresponds to an already formatted `.csv`, `.txt` or `.xlsx` file.
- **SAMPLE_SELECT**: a list containing the minimum sample size, target depth range and sample temporal range.

```
{r}
list_bio <- list_bio_wrapper(FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
                           DATA_SOURCE = "occurrence",
                           SAMPLE_SELECT = list(MIN_SAMPLE = 50, TARGET_MIN_DEPTH = 0,
                                                TARGET_MAX_DEPTH = 100, START_YEAR = 1950, STOP_YEAR = 2020))
```


Figure 1 – Synthetic diagram of the CEPHALOPOD indicating the essential list of modelling choices, quality checks and flags used in the workflow. The main steps are indicated on the left-hand side. The associated quality checks or modelling choices are displayed in the middle panels. The corresponding thresholds used for quality flags are indicated on the right-hand side. Those used in the final traffic-light quality flag are indicated in bold. Gray, yellow, green, or orange background corresponds to common, presence-only, continuous or proportions specific steps, respectively. Figure retrieved from Schickele et al. (2025).

Step 2. Initialize the CEPHALOPOD run

Now we can look at the `list_bio` object and build a vector of species identifier (WoRMS taxonomy) to extrapolate the distribution from. Here, we select all species in the *Thalassiosira* taxa. This code block can be customized depending on the taxa selection needed for your case study. **Please note**, it is important that `sp_list` is a character.

```
{r}
sp_list <- list_bio %>%
  dplyr::filter(grepl("Thalassiosira ", scientificname)) %>%
  dplyr::select(worms_id) %>%
  unique() %>% pull()
```

In the second step of the modeling process, several critical actions are taken to prepare for subsequent stages (**Figure 1** – step 2). First, a dedicated output folder is created to systematically store the results of each specieslevel run. Global parameters for modeling are defined, including environmental variables, data types (e.g., proportions), and the selection of specific modeling methods. These parameters are stored into a `CALL.Rdata` object, which is referenced by all subsequent steps. This approach minimizes memory consumption and simplifies the execution of each step. Finally, a local repository of monthly environmental climatologies is established, utilizing `.nc` data. This step is crucial to ensure a uniform set and format of environmental predictors while also optimizing memory usage.

Please note, this function defines all parameters of the run. If it is your first use of CEPHALOPOD, it is recommended to read the subsequent steps first and use this one as a parameter index description.

Parameters are the following:

- `FOLDER_NAME` name of the run folder we want to work in
- `SP_SELECT` vector of identifiers (i.e., usually WoRMS identifiers), corresponding to the species to parallelize on
- `FAST TRUE` or `FALSE`; if `TRUE`, CEPHALOPOD stops the processing of taxa that did not success at a quality check. It avoids unnecessary CPU and memory usage.
- `LOAD_FROM` load a previous `list_bio` object from another folder to be duplicated in the new `FOLDER_NAME`. It avoids repeating the initial steps of CEPHALOPOD.
- `DATA_TYPE` the output type of the data, which can influence the sub-folder architecture. See details in the corresponding function.
- `ENV_VAR` a list of `.nc` files to extract the main variable from, located in `ENV_PATH`. The names correspond to the variable name of the corresponding `.nc` file. If a `!` is specified at the start of the variable name, the variable is excluded from the list.

- **ENV_PATH** string or vector of path to the root where the `.nc` are.
- **NB_PA** number of pseudo-absences to generate
- **PER_RANDOM** by default, pseudo-absences are generated according to the density of nearby presences (Descombe et al., 2022). This is to ensure similar spatial biases between presences and pseudo-absences. This parameter controls the ratio of pseudo-absences that are sampled randomly in the background.
- **PA_ENV_STRATA** if **TRUE**, increases the pseudo-absence sampling probability in geographical cells with environmental conditions distant from the conditions of the observations. This can be useful if presences are endemic to a certain geographical region.
- **BACKGROUND_FILTER** additional background filter for finer tuning, such as selecting pseudoabsences within the sampled background of a given campaign or instrument deployment. Passed by the user in the form of a **2 column data frame, x = longitude and y = latitude** where the pseudo-absences can be sampled. Or a **path to a raster** object where pseudo-absences are sampled in non NA cells, weighted by the cell values.
- **OUTLIER** if **TRUE**, remove outliers further than 2.5 standard deviation from the mean of the observations (Knecht et al, 2023)
- **RFE** if **TRUE**, performs a Recursive Feature Elimination (Darst et al., 2018) procedure that discards predictors that do not present significant importance in explaining the patterns in the observations, relative to the ones already selected.
- **ENV_COR** numeric, selects one environmental predictor among clusters of inter-correlated environmental predictors, according to the defined threshold. Else **NULL**.
- **NFOLD** number of folds, used defined integer
- **FOLD_METHOD** method used to create the folds, integer between "kfold" and "lon"; respectively for normal k-fold or longitudinal block of observations (recommended to deal with spatial autocorrelation issues ; Roberts et al. 2017).
- **MODEL_LIST** list of algorithms to use for calibration and hyperparameter selection
- **LEVELS** maximum number of parameter values to test in each of the hyperparameter grids dimension
- **TARGET_TRANSFORMATION** path to a **function(x, REVERSE = TRUE | FALSE)** to transform the target variable prior to the model calibration step.
- **N_BOOTSTRAP** number of bootstrap to do for the projections and partial dependency plots
- **CUT** numeric or **NULL**; if numeric, quantile (between 0 and 1) at which the projections are considered to be 0. Projection patches without observation are then removed.

The function is assigned to `subfolder_list` as it also returns the list of species to parallelize on.

```
{r}
subfolder_list <- run_init(FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
                          SP_SELECT = sp_list,
                          FAST = FALSE,
                          LOAD_FROM = NULL,
                          DATA_TYPE = "presence_only",
                          ENV_VAR = c("!climatology_s_0_50", "!climatology_s_200_300"),
                          ENV_PATH = NULL, # replace by local path to environmental
predictors,
                          METHOD_PA = "density",
                          PER_RANDOM = 0.05,
                          OUTLIER = TRUE,
                          RFE = TRUE,
                          ENV_COR = 0.8,
                          NFOLD = 3,
                          FOLD_METHOD = "lon",
                          MODEL_LIST = c("GLM", "GAM", "RF", "MLP", "BRT", "SVM"),
                          LEVELS = 3,
                          TARGET_TRANSFORMATION = NULL,
                          ENSEMBLE = TRUE,
                          N_BOOTSTRAP = 10,
                          CUT = NULL)
```

Step 3. Query the selected biological data

Now that we have set all parameters needed for the run, we can retrieve the biological data for the selected taxa to extrapolate the distribution from (**Figure 1** – step 3). These data form the foundation for training and validating species distribution models. The availability and quality of this data are crucial for the success of the modeling process. **The function is built in parallel over each taxa considered.** It does not provide output in the console, as all the retrieve data are saved in a `QUERY.RData` object. As for all subsequent functions, the parameters are following:

- **FOLDER_NAME**: the name of the folder in which the run is saved
- **SUBFOLDER_NAME**: the name of all sub folders corresponding to each species to parallelize over

```
{r}
mcmapply(FUN = query_bio_wrapper,
         FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
         SUBFOLDER_NAME = subfolder_list,
         mc.cores = min(length(subfolder_list), MAX_CLUSTERS))
```

Step 4. Query the associated environmental data

We can now extract the environmental data corresponding to each biological sample at the time and location of the sample. In addition, the data is regridded and binned on a 1 x 1° monthly resolution (**Figure 1** – step 4; **Table 1**). Taxa that do not meet the minimum number of occurrence after binning are discarded. Therefore, we assign the output of this function to an updated subfolder_list object.

Please note that the list of available environmental predictors is accessible as supplementary material in [Schickele et al. \(2025\)](#), or in the `.data/features` folder if you downloaded the archive associated to this practical exercise.

```
{r}
subfolder_list <- mcmapply(FUN = query_env,
  FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
  SUBFOLDER_NAME = subfolder_list,
  mc.cores = min(length(subfolder_list), MAX_CLUSTERS)) %>%
  unlist() %>%
  na.omit(subfolder_list) %>%
  [.grep("Error", ., invert = TRUE)] %>%
  as.vector()
```

Name	Unit	Source	Depth resolution	Time range
ocean mixed layer thickness	m	WOA18	NA	1981-2010
apparent oxygen utilization	µmol.kg ⁻¹	WOA18		1900-2017
silicate concentration	µmol.kg ⁻¹	WOA18		1900-2017
nitrate concentration	µmol.kg ⁻¹	WOA18		1900-2017
dissolved oxygen concentration	µmol.kg ⁻¹	WOA18	0 – 50 m and	1900-2017
oxygen saturation	%	WOA18	100 – 1000 m	1900-2017
phosphate concentration	µmol.kg ⁻¹	WOA18		1900-2017
sea water salinity	-	WOA18		1955-2017
sea water temperature	°C	WOA18		1955-2017
co2 concentration	µmol.kg ⁻¹	OceanSoda		1982-2022
carbonate ion concentration	µmol.kg ⁻¹	OceanSoda		1982-2022
dissolved inorganic carbon concentration	µmol.kg ⁻¹	OceanSoda		1982-2022
bicarbonate ion concentration	µmol.kg ⁻¹	OceanSoda		1982-2022
sea ice concentration	-	OceanSoda		1982-2022
omega aragonite	-	OceanSoda		1982-2022
omega calcite	-	OceanSoda		1982-2022
pH total	-log([H ⁺])	OceanSoda		1982-2022
revelle factor	-	OceanSoda	Surface only	1982-2022
surface fCO2	-	OceanSoda		1982-2022
surface pCO2	µatm	OceanSoda		1982-2022
total alkalinity	µmol.kg ⁻¹	OceanSoda		1982-2022
absorption coefficient (443nm, QAA)	m ⁻¹	GMIS		2002-2017
absorption coefficient of phytoplankton (443nm, QAA)	m ⁻¹	GMIS		2002-2017
total alkalinity (SVR ensemble)	µmol.kg ⁻¹	GMIS		2002-2017
particulate backscattering coefficient (443nm, QAA)	m ⁻¹	GMIS		2002-2017
chlorophyll-a (MODISA)	mg Chl.m ⁻³	GMIS		2002-2017
diffuse attenuation coefficient (490nm, KD2)	m ⁻¹	GMIS		2002-2017

photosynthetically available radiation (400-700nm)	Ein m ⁻² .d ⁻¹	GMIS	2002-2017
primary production	mgC m ⁻² .d ⁻¹	GMIS	1997-2010
particulate organic carbon concentration	mgC.m ⁻³	CMEMS	1998-2010
diatom chlorophyll-a	mgChl.m ⁻³	CMEMS	1998-2020
dinophytes chlorophyll-a	mgChl.m ⁻³	CMEMS	1998-2020
picophytoplankton chlorophyll-a	mgChl.m ⁻³	CMEMS	1998-2020
prochlorophytes chlorophyll-a	mgChl.m ⁻³	CMEMS	1998-2020
prokaryotes chlorophyll-a	mgChl.m ⁻³	CMEMS	1998-2020
green algae chlorophyll-a	mgChl.m ⁻³	CMEMS	1998-2020
microphytoplankton chlorophyll-a	mgChl.m ⁻³	CMEMS	1998-2020
nanophytoplankton chlorophyll-a	mgChl.m ⁻³	CMEMS	1998-2020
haptophytes chlorophyll-a	mgChl.m ⁻³	CMEMS	1998-2020
eddy kinetic energy	cm ² .s ⁻²	AVISO	1993-2021
finite size Lyapunov exponent	d ⁻¹	AVISO	2000-2021

Table 1 - Collection of observation-based, monthly-resolved environmental features at the global scale and available in this course material. Figure based on Schickele et al. (2025; supplementary data S1)

Step 5. Generate pseudo-absences

For occurrence data, we need to artificially generate pseudo-absences to have a balanced dataset between 0 and 1's (**Figure 1** – step 5). This balance is crucial for accurate model training and predictive performance and best practices recommend pseudo-absences following the same biases as presences. They are by default generated following the nearby presence density. The function provides a [.PDF](#) file with the presence and pseudo-absence distribution in the geographical space (or the observations for continuous or proportion data types).

```
{r}
mcmapply(FUN = pseudo_abs,
         FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
         SUBFOLDER_NAME = subfolder_list,
         mc.cores = min(length(subfolder_list), MAX_CLUSTERS))
```

Step 6. Selection of environmental parameters and input quality checks

In step 6, we rigorously check the biological and environmental dataset quality (**Figure 1** – step 6). First, we identify and handle biological outliers in the data to avoid introducing bias in the model training and extrapolated maps. Then, we assess the quality and relevance of environmental predictor variables used by discarding correlated environmental predictors and discarding predictors that do not explain a significant portion of the observed data (e.g., sea ice cover for a tropical species presents a flat response). This step is crucial for a parsimonious feature set. The function updates `subfolder_list` with the species passing the quality check on the selected predictors. Finally, we perform a Multivariate Environmental

Similarity Surface (MESS) analysis (Elith et al., 2010) to identify the geographical areas outside the range of environmental values in which the model has been trained (i.e., environmental extrapolation).

Several .PDF files are provided in this steps, including a dendrogram of environmental predictor correlation, an *a priori* predictor importance and ranking of the predictors, as well as the corresponding loss after which, adding a predictor would not significantly increase the model performance.

```
{r}
subfolder_list <- mcmapply(FUN = query_check,
                          FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
                          SUBFOLDER_NAME = subfolder_list,
                          mc.cores = min(length(subfolder_list), MAX_CLUSTERS)) %>%
  unlist() %>%
  na.omit(subfolder_list) %>%
  as.vector()
```

Step 7. Define cross-validation splits

Now that the input data have been thoroughly quality checked, we can create splits and resampling folds to facilitate the training and assessment of species distribution models (Figure 1 – step 7). Proper partitioning of data is essential for robust modeling results, and assessing model performance in reproducing the observed patterns. The model training design is oriented around a *n-time* cross validation between train and test set to find the best hyperparameters for each algorithm.

```
{r}
mcmapply(FUN = folds,
         FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
         SUBFOLDER_NAME = subfolder_list,
         mc.cores = min(length(subfolder_list), MAX_CLUSTERS))
```

Step 8. Define algorithm hyperparameters

Each algorithm is associated to a set of hyperparameter to best reproduce the observed biological target. This step focuses on configuring hyperparameters for training the species distribution models algorithms (Figure 1 – step 8). These hyperparameters dictate the model's behavior during training and significantly influence model performance.

```
{r}
hyperparameter(FOLDER_NAME = run_name)
```

Step 9. Algorithm training

At this stage, we defined all necessary parameters and quality checked all input data. Therefore, we can start to fit species distribution models to the data (**Figure 1** – step 9). We employ various modeling algorithms, such as Generalized Linear Models (**GLM**), Generalized Additive Models (**GAM**), Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machines (**SVM**), Boosted Regression Trees (**BRT**) and Multilayer Perceptrons (**MLP**), to capture the relationships between environmental features and the biological target(s).

Please note that from this step onward, all outputs are saved in a **MODEL.Rdata** object in each species corresponding sub folder. The input parameters remain the same as in the previous steps.

```
{r}
mcmapply(FUN = model_wrapper,
         FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
         SUBFOLDER_NAME = subfolder_list,
         mc.cores = min(length(subfolder_list), MAX_CLUSTERS))
```

Step 10. Algorithm evaluation

To assess each of the algorithm's performance (**Figure 1** – step 10), we perform a serie of quality checks on the evaluation dataset. **Please check** the methods in [Schickele et al. \(2025\)](#) for a complete benchmark of the CEPHALOPOD evaluation and quality checks.

- **FIT**: the metric quantifying the fitting performance of the algorithm. How well does it reproduces the patterns in the observed data? We use a threshold of Continuous Boyce Index > 0.5 for presence only data ([Leroy et al., 2018](#)), and adjusted R2 > 0.25 for continuous and proportion data ([Schickele et al., 2025](#); [Waldock et al. 2022](#)).
- **VIP**: the variable importance (PDF output), that quantifies the contribution of each environmental predictor. We only consider algorithm with their top 3 environmental predictors explaining at least 50 % of the variance in the observations. This ensures a clear trend in the interpretability in the algorithms.

```
{r}
mcmapply(FUN = eval_wrapper,
         FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
         SUBFOLDER_NAME = subfolder_list,
         mc.cores = min(length(subfolder_list), MAX_CLUSTERS))
```

Step 11. Spatial projections

All algorithm that successfully passed the evaluation step (if **FAST = TRUE**) are considered of sufficient quality to built spatial projections (**Figure 1** – step 11). We retrain a full model with the parameters and hyperparameters previously selected and perform spatial projections for *n*-bootstrap resamples to estimate the associated uncertainty. This ensures that the projected model has seen all available biological data, with validated algorithm parameter and hyperparameters. A quality check is performed on the bootstrap-level uncertainty estimation.

- **NSD**: the normalized standard deviation, quantifying the uncertainty between bootstraps at each gridcell, averaged over all grid-cells of the projection domain. We only consider algorithms with a **NSD** under 0.5, to ensure robust spatial projections.

```
{r}
mcmapply(FUN = proj_wrapper,
         FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
         SUBFOLDER_NAME = subfolder_list,
         mc.cores = min(length(subfolder_list), MAX_CLUSTERS))
```

Step 12. Building the outputs

Following the projections, CEPHALOPOD provides a summarized **PDF** output (**Figure 1** – step 12) of the each projections and quality checks for each taxa, algorithm and ensembles, unless **FAST** is set to **FALSE**. All validated algorithms are concatenated in an ensemble projection and the **NSD** is computed at the ensemble level. This means that we measure algorithm disagreement within the ensemble. We only consider ensembles with a **NSD** under 0.3, to ensure sufficient agreement between ensemble members. The projections for both algorithm and ensemble level are provided in a monthly resolution.

```
{r}
mcmapply(FUN = standard_maps,
         FOLDER_NAME = run_name,
         SUBFOLDER_NAME = subfolder_list,
         mc.cores = min(length(subfolder_list), MAX_CLUSTERS))
```

Finally, all PDF files present in each species folder can be summarized in a unique summary for users, concatenating all quality checks and outputs of the present workbench ecosystem run.

```
{r}  
user_synthesis(FOLDER_NAME = run_name)
```

Supplementary analysis such as diversity estimates can be performed by any user based on the information, data and output stored in the **QUERY** and **MODEL.Rdata** objects.

6. Practical guide

6.1 Learning goals

By the end of this practical, you will be able to:

- Use an ensemble species distribution modeling pipeline to project the biogeographic distribution of a marine target organism.
- Run a state-of-the-art habitat modeling R workflow independently on your laptop.
- Understand how environmental factors influence the ecological niches of marine species.
- Recognize the impact of key methodological decisions - including data bias correction, selection of predictors, choice of background data, modeling algorithms, and evaluation metrics - on the results of habitat models.
- Critically assess the quality and reliability of the habitat projections you generate.
- Interpret spatial patterns and variability in the habitat of your target species.
- Propose further macroecological analyses and identify potential methodological improvements.

6.2 Step by step instructions

6.2.1 Prerequisite

- This section assumes you have completed the previous steps, including the successful installation of the CEPHALOPOD pipeline on your local machine and a basic understanding of the pipeline's structure and parameters.
- If you are unsure about any step, please revisit the earlier sections and documents before proceeding.

6.2.2 Choose your species to model

- Open the `master.R` script and run the header panel to initialize your R session.
- Ensure that no errors occur during library loading (from the `00_config.R` file).
- Use the `list_bio_wrapper()` function to read the `.data/biological_input.csv` file. This will display the list of available species for modeling.
- Modify the `sp_list` variable to include the `worms_id` corresponding to your species of interest.
- For more information on your species, you can refer to its page on the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS).

6.2.3 Initialize your CEPHALOPOD run

- Set the `ENV_PATH` and `ENV_VAR` parameters in `run_init()` to specify the environmental layers you want to use. These can be chosen based on known ecological drivers for your species.
- Set the `DATA_TYPE` parameter to `"presence_only"` (required for this practical).
- You may adjust other parameters if you wish, based on the descriptions provided in the earlier sections. However, we recommend starting with a run using default settings, followed by an additional run with modified parameters.
- Running `run_init()` will create an output folder with subfolders per species in your `./output` directory. The run parameters are stored in the `CALL.RData` object.

6.2.4. Query biological observations and environmental data

- Run Steps 3 and 4 of the pipeline to load biological observations and associate them with environmental predictors.
- The results will be saved in the `QUERY.RData` object located in each species-specific subfolder.

6.2.5. Generate pseudo-absences

- Execute Step 5 of the pipeline to generate pseudo-absence data.
- This step will update `QUERY.RData` and generate a `.pdf` visualization.
- Use the `.pdf` file to inspect the spatial distribution of both occurrences and pseudo-absences, including their latitudinal and longitudinal patterns.
- Reflect on the output: Is there any evidence of spatial sampling bias that might affect your interpretation of the final model results? Should you re-start CEPHALOPOD with different parameters?

6.2.6. Process and quality check the input data

- Run the step 6 of the pipeline to perform the input quality checks.

- Check the [02_env_cor.pdf](#), to understand how your environmental predictors are correlated at the observation location. One selected predictor may be a proxy of its respective cluster, this will help for the interpretation of the final maps.
- Check the [03_feature_pre_selection.pdf](#), to understand which environmental predictor has been selected after the RFE, and which ones contain redundant pattern with the already selected ones.
- Check the [04_feature_verification.pdf](#) to have an overview of the environmental predictor distribution on the target, and the reason they were selected or not in the final predictor set.
- Check the [log.txt](#) file in the species folder to have a complete tracing of the environmental predictor selection and outlier detection.
- Now that the input data is quality checked and processed, we can proceed with the modelling steps!

6.2.7. Run and evaluate the algorithms

- Run the step 7 to 10 of the pipeline, to prepare the cross-validation splits, define hyperparameters, calibrate and evaluate the algorithms. Algorithm computation may take several minutes.
- Check the [04_variable_importance.pdf](#) together with the [log.txt](#) file to extract information about the algorithm predictive performance and variance explained.
- Assess the performance of the algorithms, which ones did (or not) pass the quality check (CBI > 0.5 for **presence only** data).
- Assess the variance explained by each environmental predictor. Which are the most important drivers? Do they make ecological sense given your knowledge on the considered species? Do the different algorithms agree? A close inspection to this is key to understand effect and contribution of each predictor in shaping the estimated species distribution.

6.2.8. Run the projections

- Run the step 11 of the pipeline to perform the bootstrap spatial projections.
- Open the [log.txt](#) file to assess which algorithm passed the projection uncertainty quality check.
- You can also open the **MODEL.RData** object and assess the information in **MODEL_LIST**, or in the associated algorithm elements of the list.

6.2.9. Visualize your outputs

- Run the step 12 of the pipeline to generate the [05_standard_maps.pdf](#)
- Open this .pdf file and assess the macroecological distribution of your species.
- Does the distribution match your expectations, the observed data, or the scientific knowledge on this species?

- How is the uncertainty distributed spatially? Are any geographical regions subject to extrapolation outside environmental conditions of the observations?
- Is the ensemble matching the expectations, observed data or scientific knowledge on this species?
- Do algorithms agree within the ensemble?
- Is the global distribution pattern, or the habitat suitability values affected by seasonality? If so, which geographical areas present the highest seasonal changes?
- Given the environmental predictor selected and variance explained, what macroecological interpretation can you do from the information present in the [03_feature_pre_selection.pdf](#), [04_variable_importance.pdf](#) and [05_standard_maps.pdf](#)?

6.2.10. Take stock

- What have you learnt?
- How would you adapt this framework to your current research questions?

Please note that this practical only showcased the distribution modelling for one species with presence only observations. As mentioned in the introduction, the ecosystem workbench is scalable to several hundreds of species, highly automated, and adapted for abundance, biomass, or metagenomic read data, offering broad application possibilities.

7. References

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Please note that most references are included in the CEPHALOPOD publication (Schickele et al., 2025). If you are interested in using the pipeline after this course, we recommend reading the publication and reference therein.